

Vertical distribution and comparative zoogeographical characteristic of dipteran fauna (Insecta: Diptera) according to the vegetation belts of the Pirin and Rila Mountains

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Abstract: A total of 1351 species from 63 families (759 species from the Pirin Mts. and 1003 species from the Rila Mts.) have been recorded from the two mountains so far. The low degree of similarity (46.2%) of the fauna between these mountains is related to their natural features and insufficient research. The greatest number of species has been found in the zone of the beech forests (409 species or 55.1% from Pirin Mts. and 736 species or 73.4% from the Rila Mts.). The degree of similarity between the dipteran fauna of the different vegetation belts of the two mountains ranges from 0% to 46.6%. The dipterans belong to 92 areogeographical categories, divided into two supergroups: 1) species with Mediterranean type of distribution: more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic (49 species or 6.5% from Pirin Mts. and 48 species or 4.8% from the Rila Mts.); 2) species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution: more eurybiontic and widely distributed in the Palaearctic (710 species or 93.5% from Pirin Mts. and 955 species or 95.2% from the Rila Mts.). The Holomediterranean and Mediterranean-Central Asian forms (from 0.6% to 1.3%) are the best represented in the first group. The European, Holarctic, Holoeurosiberian and Transpalaearctic taxa (from 7.8% to 19.0%) prevail in the second group. A total of 12-13 species (from 1.2% to 1.7%) are endemics. The distribution of the zoogeographical categories in the separate vegetation belts of the mountains is scrutinised.

Key words: Diptera, Pirin Mts., Rila Mts., areogeography, zoogeography, faunistic composition, Bulgaria

Introduction

The first data on Diptera from the Pirin Mts. are reported by DRENSKY (1929). In 82 publications there are data related to dipterans of the mountain (HUBENOV, 2015b). The first data on Diptera from the Rila Mts. are reported by JOAKIMOFF (1899) and NEDELKOV (1909, 1910, 1912). In 120 publications there are data concerning dipterans of the mountain (HUBENOV, 2016).

The data are fragmentary, concern separated parts of the mountains and are scattered in different articles, which are not specially referred to the Pirin or Rila Mts. There are more systematic studies (presented differently for each of the mountains) for the families Limoniidae, Cecidomyiidae, Simuliidae, Chironomidae, Syrphidae, Agromyzidae, Chloropidae, Muscidae and Tachinidae. There

are systematic studies on the Pirin Mts. for the family Tachinidae (HUBENOV, 1992) and the Rila Mts. – for the families Simuliidae (KOVACHEV, 2000) and Chironomidae (STOICHEV, 2000a, 2000b, 2002, 2004; STOICHEV & CERNEV, 2001, STOICHEV & DANOVA, 2003). Generalised investigations on the tachinid fauna of both mountains are reported by HUBENOV (2015b, 2016).

The aim of this work is to present the distribution of Diptera in the vegetation belts of the Pirin and Rila Mountains, as well as to make a comparative zoogeographical analysis of the fauna.

Study area, materials and methods

The two mountains vary in respect of their physical geographical features. **PIRIN MTS.** are situated between the valleys of the Struma and Mesta Rivers, south of the Rila Mts., from which are separated by the Predel Col (1140 m a.s.l.).

The Paril Col (1174 m a.s.l.) separates the Pirin Mts. from the situated in the south Slavyanka Mts. The Pirin Mts. stretch northwest-southeast and is about 80 km long and 40 km wide. The maximum height at Vihren Peak is 2914.3 m a.s.l. The total area of the mountains is 2585 km². They are divided into North, Middle and South Pirin. In the Pleistocene glacial forms have been formed in the Pirin Mts. Gravity forms of alpine type are characteristic of its high parts. Climatically the Pirin Mts. belong to the Continental-Mediterranean climatic region and include parts of the Maleshevska-Pirin Low Mountain, Mestenski and Mountain climatic areas (STANEV, 1991). Glacial lakes are situated in the cirques of the granite part of Northern Pirin, whereas the marble part is relatively anhydrous. The Pirin Mts. belong to the region of the Illyrian Province of the European deciduous forest area. The vegetation is differentiated in a system of six vegetation belts (STOJANOV, 1966; VELCHEV et al., 1982, 1989; VELCHEV, TONKOV, 1986; BONDEV, 1991, 1997, 2002; VELCHEV, 1997, 2002): 1) Xerothermic oak forests, best presented in the west and south hillsides up to 600-700 m a.s.l.; 2) Mesophylic and xeromesophylic mixed forests, well presented in the south-west and east hillsides from 600-700 m a.s.l. to 900-1000 m a.s.l.; 3) Beech forests, best presented in the middle and south parts of the mountain from 900-1000 m a.s.l. to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.; 4) Coniferous forests from 1300-1600 m a.s.l. to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.; 5) Subalpine vegetation from 2000 to 2500 m a.s.l.; 6) Alpine vegetation above 2400-2500 m a.s.l. For the coniferous zone of the marble part of Northern Pirin, the Mediterranean plant formation of *Pinus leucodermis* Ant. is typical. The Pirin Mts. belong to the Rila-Rhodope zoogeographical region and have an Eurosiberian and Submediterranean faunistic character in the lower parts (GEORGIEV, 1982, 2002). The territory of the Pirin National Park includes 40332 ha with the reserves Bayuvi Dupki-Dzhindzhiritsa (2873 ha) and Yulen (3156 ha). The park's boundary descends to 800-900 m a.s.l. but usually lies significantly higher (above 1300-1700 m a.s.l.).

RILA MTS. are situated north of the Pirin Mts. They are connected with the Verila, Ihtimanska Sredna Gora and Rhodope Mountains through the Klisurska (1025 m a.s.l.), Borovetska (1305 m a.s.l.), Yundolska (1375 m a.s.l.) and Avramova (1295 m a.s.l.) Cols. The Rila Mts. stretch west-east and are over 70 km

long and 50 km wide. The maximum height at Musala Peak is 2925 m a.s.l. The total area of the mountains is 2629 km². They are divided into four parts: North-west, Central, East and South-west. The Rila Mts. are a silicate massif consisting essentially of granites. In the Pleistocene glacial forms have been formed. Gravity forms of alpine type are characteristic of the high parts. The Rila Mts. are under the influence of the Intermediate-Continental and Continental-Mediterranean climatic regions. They include parts of the Rila-Osogovo and Mountain climatic regions (STANEV, 1991). In the cirques of the mountains 190 glacial lakes are situated. The Rila Mts. belong to the region of the Illyrian Province of the European deciduous forest area. The vegetation is differentiated in a system of six vegetation belts (STOJANOV, 1966; VELCHEV et al., 1982, 1989; VELCHEV, TONKOV, 1986; BONDEV, 1991, 1997, 2002; VELCHEV, 1997, 2002): 1) Xerothermic oak forests, best presented in the north-east, west and south-west hillsides to 500-700 m a.s.l.; 2) Mesophylic and xeromesophylic mixed forests, well presented in the west, east and south-east hillsides from 600-700 m a.s.l. to 900-1000 m a.s.l.; 3) Beech forests, best presented in the north, north-east and west parts of the mountains from 900-1000 m a.s.l. to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.; 4) Coniferous forests, best presented in the north, east and south hillsides from 1500-1600 m a.s.l. to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.; 5) Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 a.s.l. to 2500 m a.s.l.; 6) Alpine vegetation – above 2400-2500 m a.s.l. Under the human impact, the vegetation has undergone destructive changes, expressed most strongly in the first two zones. The boundaries between the vegetation belts are not defined clearly and depending on the exposure, topography and human activities there are mixed zones up to 200-300 m a.s.l. The Rila Mts. belong to the Rila-Rhodope zoogeographical region and have an Eurosiberian faunistic character (GEORGIEV, 1982, 2002). The mountains are the richest area in endemics (268) and relicts (230) in Bulgaria (HUBENOV, 2008). The territory of the Rila National Park includes 81046 ha with the Parangalitsa (1509 ha), Central Rila (12393.7 ha), Ibar (2248.6 ha) and Skakavitsa (70.8 ha) Reserves. The park's boundary rarely descends below 1000 m a.s.l. and usually lies higher (to 1500-2000 m a.s.l.). The Rila Monastery Nature Park (27270 ha) with the Rila Monastery Forest Reserve (3678 ha) is also included in the moun-

tains' territory.

The material from the Pirin Mts. was collected from 77 localities after 1914. From the western and south-western slopes of the mountains, the territory above 300 m a.s.l. is included. The material from the Rila Mts. was collected from 160 localities after 1890. Some collectors at the beginning of the last century did not give accurate localities on the labels and indicated only Pirin Mts. or Rila Mts. There are no exact localities for 47 species from the Pirin Mts. and 111 species from the Rila Mts. For a number of widespread and numerous species, the authors did not give the localities and mentioned they occurred everywhere. Such species are included in the review only if they are reported from the Pirin Mts. or Rila Mts. The main part of the material is stored in the National Museum of Natural History and the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research. A number of foreign entomologists have been collecting and publishing materials from Bulgaria, containing data about the Pirin and Rila Mts. The species distribution in the vegetation belts is determined according to the altitude and the landscape of the localities.

Zoogeographical analysis for the species categorisation was used. This method allows obtaining data information about species complexes with different zoogeographical character based on the published data regarding species distribution and results of the faunistic research. The classification of the areas follows DE LATTIN (1967), MALICKY et al. (1983), GORODKOV (1984) and VIGNA TAGLIANTI et al. (1999). To compare the fauna, Czekanowski-Dice-Sørensen coefficient of similarity was used.

Abbreviations used: ♦ – presence of the species in the Pirin Mts., ● – presence of the species in the Rila Mts., ? – uncertain data or lack of data, +++ – species without exact locality in the Pirin Mts. or Rila Mts., **atm** – Afrotropical-Mediterranean, **ba** – Boreoalpine, **ban** – Balkan-Anatolian, **bm** – Boreomontane, **cee** – Central and East European, **cse** – Central and South European, **csean** – Central and South European-Anatolian, **csee** – Central and South-East European, **cseean** – Central and South-East European-Anatolian, **cseeit** – Central and South-East European-Iran-Turanian, **cseel** – Central and South-East European-Lebanonian, **cseit** – Central and South European-Iran-Turanian, **csena** – Central and South European-North African, **des** – Disjunct Eurosiberian, **dp** – Disjunct

Palaeartic, **dpo** – Disjunct Palaeartic-Oriental, **e** – European, **ean** – European-Anatolian, **eanna** – European-Anatolian-North African, **Eb** – Balkan endemic, **Ebg** – Bulgarian endemic, **Ebs** – Balkan subendemic, **eca** – European-Central Asian, **eeca** – East European-Central Asian, **eit** – European-Iran-Turanian, **em** – East Mediterranean, **ena** – European-North African, **Er** – Regional endemic, **esanca** – Eurosiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian, **esca** – Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **ess** – European and South Siberian, **eswa** – European-South-West Asian, **et** – European-Turanian, **ewca** – European-West Central Asian, **h** – Holarctic, **h*** – species introduced in North America, **ha** – Holarctic-Australian, **hat** – Holarctic-Afrotropical, **hata** – Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian, **hn** – Holarctic-Neotropical, **hnat** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical, **hno** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental, **ho** – Holarctic-Oriental, **hoa** – Holarctic-Oriental-Australian, **hoes** – Holoeurosiberian, **hom** – Holomediterranean, **hop** – Holopalaeartic, **hpt** – Holarctic-Paleotropical, **hpta** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian, **hptn** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical, **I** – introduced species (immigrants), **k** – Cosmopolitan, **m** – montane, **mca** – Mediterranean-Central Asian, **mss** – Mediterranean and South Siberian, **msws** – Mediterranean and South-West Siberian, **mt** – Mediterranean-Turanian, **mwca** – Mediterranean-West Central Asian, **nemit** – North-East Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian, **nm** – North Mediterranean, **nmca** – North Mediterranean-Central Asian, **nmt** – North Mediterranean-Turanian, **om** – Oriental-Mediterranean, **pa** – Palaeartic-Australian, **pat** – Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **pata** – Palaeartic-Afrotropical-Australian, **po** – Palaeartic-Oriental, **poa** – Palaeartic-Oriental-Australian, **ppt** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical, **ppta** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian, **ptm** – Paleotropical-Mediterranean, **se** – South European, **see** – South-east European, **sena** – South European-North African, **sess** – South European and South Siberian, **sk** – Semicosmopolitan, **sp** – South Palaeartic, **spat** – South Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **spta** – South Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian, **tp** – Transpalaeartic, **wces** – West and Central Eurosiberian, **wcp** – West and Central Palaeartic, **wes** – West Eurosiberian, **wesanca** – West Eurosiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian, **wesca** – West Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **wesit** – West Eurosiberian-Iran-Turanian, **wp** – West Palaeartic, **wpat** – West Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **wpo** – West Palaeartic-Oriental.

Results and discussion

A total of 1351 species of Diptera (33.3% of the species found in Bulgaria) that belong to 63 families have been established in the Pirin and Rila Mountains so far (Tables 1, 2). The family Tachinidae was the most numerous with 231 species, followed by Syrphidae – 163, Limoniidae – 113, Chloropidae – 87, Cecidomyiidae – 85, Muscidae – 75, Chironomidae – 57 and Agromyzidae – 53 species. The remaining families contained from one to 39 species. A total of 759 dipteran species (18.5% of the Bulgarian species) from 44 families were recorded from the Pirin Mts. and 1003 species (25.1% of the Bulgarian species) from 58 families were established from the Rila Mts. A total of 403 species were common for both mountains, while 339 species were found only in the Pirin Mts., and 600 species – only in the Rila Mts. The relatively low degree of similarity of the fauna of Diptera between the two mountains (46.2%) is due to their specific natural conditions and insufficient studies. The degree of similarity was higher (over 60%) in separated families that are better studied. The wide distribution of the dipterans suggests similar fauna of the mountains in Bulgaria. Most Diptera species have vast ranges and the endemics are exceptional (1-1.5% of the Bulgarian species – HUBENOV, 2008a). Usually they are newly described taxa or rare species with unclear distribution. The taxa presence in most cases was connected with the exploration of the corresponding mountain region. This was evident when comparing the established species with regard to the localities they were found.

Six areas of detailed research are outlined in the Pirin Mts. (over 70 species found: HUBENOV, 2015b). First are the surroundings of Bansko (132 species) and Melnik (139 species), the most visited places at the foot of the mountains. The popular resorts and starting points for entering the Pirin Mts., Sandanski and Lilyanovo Villages, Popinalaka and Razlog (from 77 to 92 species) also form a group of well-studied regions. Of the inner parts of the mountains, the surroundings of the chalets Banderitsa, Vihren, Gotse Delchev, Yavorov and Demyanitsa are better studied (from 23 to 53 species). Usually the localities from which material has been collected are concentrated around the popular tourist centers or routes.

Five areas of detailed research are outlined in the Rila Mts. (with over 80 species estab-

lished: HUBENOV, 2016). First are the surroundings of the Rila Monastery (266 species) and Borovets (179 species), the most visited places of the mountains. The popular starting points for entering the Rila Mts., Blagoevgrad and Yundola (89-98 species), form a group of well-studied regions. The Parangalitsa Reserve (120 species), where there is a research base of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, is also well studied. Of the other parts of the mountains, the surroundings of Belovo, Kostenets, Dolna Banya, Govedarts Village, Dupnitsa and the Predela Area (from 36 to 47 species) are better studied. Of the inner parts of the mountains, the surroundings of Kravarsko Dere, Kirilova Polyana, the valley of Rilska Reka River, the Slavovo Area, and the chalets Malyovitsa and Musala (from 30 to 53 species) are better studied. Also here the localities from which a material has been collected are concentrated around the popular tourist centres.

At present, significant parts of both mountains remain unexplored and material has not been collected. This relates both to the difficulties when approaching the terrain and the insufficient investigation of the specific families. The number of the established species probably represents about 45-55% of the actual species composition of the studied territory. The dipterans are a highly mobile group and after further studies the number of the recorded taxa might reach 50-60% of the species composition of most families found in the country. The Diptera fauna of the Rila Mts. is better studied than that of the Pirin Mts. This is evident when comparing the number of localities from which material is collected, the first publications, the number of publications and the taxonomic review of the established families (Table 1, 2).

A total of 564 species have been established in the protected areas of the Rila Mts. (HUBENOV 2016: Rila National Park – 379 species and Rila Monastery Nature Park – 304 species). In comparison with the Central Balkan National Park [184 species (HUBENOV et al., 2000)], East Rhodopes [279 species (HUBENOV, 2004)], Vitosha Mts. [1000 species (HUBENOV, 2014)] and Pirin National Park [557 species (HUBENOV 2015b)] the dipteran fauna of the Rila Mts. is commensurable with the fauna of the Pirin Mts. The number of taxa recorded from the Rila Mts. significantly exceeds that of the Central Balkan National Park and East Rhodopes, and decreases vis-a-vis Vitosha Mts. Vitosha Mt. is the

Table 1. Dipteran insects (Insecta: Diptera) of the Pirin and Rila Mountains

Families	Total number of the species of the two mountains		Species of the Pirin Mt.		Species of the Rila Mt.	
	number	%	number	%	number	%
NEMATOCERA	397	29.40	200	26.35	294	29.31
Tipulidae	9	0.66			9	0.90
Limoniidae	113	8.37	84	11.06	62	6.18
Pediciidae	18	1.33	9	1.18	13	1.30
Blephariceridae	2	0.15			2	0.20
Bibionidae	4	0.30			4	0.40
Mycetophilidae	29	2.15	15	1.98	14	1.40
Bolitophilidae	7	0.52	5	0.66	4	0.40
Diadocidiidae	1	0.07	1	0.13	1	0.10
Keroplastidae	6	0.44	3	0.39	3	0.30
Macroceridae	5	0.37	4	0.53	4	0.40
Sciaridae	4	0.30			4	0.40
Cecidomyiidae	85	6.29	54	7.11	65	6.48
Trichoceridae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Scatopsidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Ptychopteridae	2	0.15	1	0.13	1	0.10
Culicidae	9	0.66			9	0.90
Simuliidae	37	2.74	10	1.32	37	3.69
Ceratopogonidae	7	0.52	1	0.13	6	0.60
Chironomidae	57	4.22	13	1.71	53	5.28
BRACHYCERA ORTHORRHAPHA	144	10.66	53	6.98	108	10.77
Coenomyiidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Stratiomyidae	14	1.04	12	1.58	5	0.50
Rhagionidae	9	0.66	8	1.05	5	0.50
Tabanidae	26	1.93	5	0.66	25	2.49
Acroceridae	1	0.07	1	0.13		
Bombyliidae	9	0.66			9	0.90
Therevidae	2	0.15			2	0.20
Asilidae	30	2.22	11	1.45	23	2.29
Empididae	15	1.11	7	0.92	8	0.80
Hybotidae	7	0.52	3	0.39	5	0.50
Dolichopodidae	30	2.22	6	0.79	25	2.49
BRACHYCERA CYCLORRHAPHA	809	59.92	506	66.67	601	59.92
Platypezidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Phoridae	3	0.22	2	0.26	1	0.10
Pipunculidae	16	1.18	14	1.84	5	0.50
Syrphidae	163	12.07	49	6.46	149	14.86
Conopidae	21	1.56	2	0.26	20	1.99
Tephritidae	10	0.74	2	0.26	8	0.80
Piophilidae	1	0.07	1	0.13		
Lauxaniidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Cremifaniidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Chamaemyiidae	12	0.89	12	1.58	1	0.10
Sciomyzidae	2	0.15			2	0.20
Sepsidae	1	0.07	1	0.13		
Agromyzidae	53	3.93	15	1.98	48	4.79
Opomyzidae	3	0.22	3	0.39	2	0.20
Carnidae	5	0.37	5	0.66		
Milichiidae	4	0.30	4	0.53	1	0.10
Chloropidae	87	6.44	72	9.49	61	6.08
Heleomyzidae	2	0.15			2	0.20
Sphaeroceridae	4	0.30	2	0.26	2	0.20

Table 1. Continued

Families	Total number of the species of the two mountains		Species of the Pirin Mt.		Species of the Rila Mt.	
	number	%	number	%	number	%
Camillidae	1	0.07	1	0.13		
Drosophilidae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Diastatidae	1	0.07	1	0.13	1	0.10
Ephyridae	39	2.89	33	4.35	26	2.59
Hippoboscidae	4	0.30	2	0.26	2	0.20
Scathophagidae	2	0.15			2	0.20
Anthomyiidae	3	0.22	1	0.13	3	0.30
Fanniidae	6	0.44	6	0.79	2	0.20
Muscidae	75	5.55	49	6.45	55	5.48
Calliphoridae	14	1.04	3	0.39	14	1.40
Sarcophagidae	38	2.81	18	2.37	24	2.39
Rhinophoridae	1	0.07			1	0.10
Gasterophilidae	3	0.22			3	0.30
Tachinidae	231	17.11	203	26.74	162	16.15
Families	63		44	69.84	58	92.06
Species	1351		759	56.18	1003	74.24

most well-studied Bulgarian mountain and its whole territory is used for comparison (not only Vitosha Nature Park), while the Central Balkan National Park is poorly studied with respect to the two-winged insects. When comparing the whole mountain with the Vitosha Mt., there is no difference in the number of the established species. The last studies on Diptera of the Pirin Mts. (HUBENOV 2015b) allow the fauna families to be compared with these of the Rila Mts. It is expected, after further investigations, the species composition of Diptera from the Pirin Mts. to exceed most of the Bulgarian mountains. This is owing to the wide variety of natural habitats, as well as to the geographical location, which the mountains occupy in South-West Bulgaria, on the border between the Eurosiberian and Mediterranean Palaearctic subregions. Further, the Rila Mts. are expected to be similar to the most of the Bulgarian high mountains in terms of species composition of Diptera. This relates to the natural habitats of the mountain, as well as to the wide distribution of the dipterans, their high mobility and poorly expressed endemism. The great number of species, established in the Rila Monastery Nature Park (commensurable with the Rila National Park), is related to the fact that the surroundings of the Rila Monastery is the most visited region of the Rila Mts.

Despite its limited development, in the xerothermic oak forest belt of the Pirin Mts. 273 species (36.8%) were established. This is connected with its open spaces enabling species

from the Sandanski-Petrich Valley and the belt above it to penetrate. In the same belt of the Rila Mts. the number of species was smaller by 11.3% (25.5%, or 256 species). In this mountain, the xerothermic oak forests were with quite limited development but here also in the open areas species from neighbouring valleys penetrate. Most taxa were found in the beech forests (409 species or 55.1% in the Pirin Mt. and 736 species or 73.4% in the Rila Mts.) and the mesophilic and xeromesophilic mixed forests (349 species or 47.0% in the Pirin Mts. and 351 species or 35.0% in the Rila Mts.). The border between beech and coniferous forests of the Pirin Mts. and Rila Mts. is not clear and depending on the exposure, relief and anthropogenic impact, there are wide areas of mixing. This determined the high species richness in the beech belt, the great number of common species and the similarity of the dipteran fauna from vegetation belts 2, 3 and 4 for each mountain. When comparing the respective belts between the two mountains (Table 3) the degree of similarity was low (from 30.7% to 46.6%). Regarding the hypsometric belts, the maximum number of species was recorded between 900 and 1300 m a.s.l. in the Pirin Mts. and between 1000 and 1500 m a.s.l. in the Rila Mts. For family Tachinidae, such investigations have been carried out for the whole country and the maximum number of species was established between 400 and 1000 m a.s.l. as there are differences in the mountains of ± 200 m (HUBENOV, 1993, 1995, 2015c). There were considerable dif-

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Eloeophila trimaculata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)		2389	e												
<i>Euphyllidorea lineola</i> (Meigen, 1804)		2389	wp												
<i>Neolimnomyia (Brachylimnophila) nemoralis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1230-1810	1147-2389	tp			♦	♦					•		•	
<i>Phyllidorea (Macrolabina) alexanderi</i> (Stary, 1974)	1750		Ebg			♦	♦								
<i>Phyllidorea (Paraphyllidorea) fulvonervosa</i> (Schummel, 1829)		1876	des												
<i>Phyllidorea (Phyllidorea) ferruginea</i> (Meigen, 1818)		1700	esca												
<i>Pitaria fuscipennis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1960-2914		des			♦	♦	♦	♦						
* <i>Prionolabis cognata</i> (Lackschewitz 1940)	1200-1700		Eb			♦	♦								
<i>Prionolabis hospes</i> (Egger, 1863)	1300-2200	1360-2389	cse			♦	♦	♦				•		•	
<i>Pseudolimnophila (Pseudolimnophila) lucorum</i> (Meigen, 1818)		1147	esca									•			
<i>Pseudolimnophila (Pseudolimnophila) septium</i> (Verrall, 1886)	2100	1147	eit			♦	♦					•			
<i>Hexatoma (Hexatoma) bicolor</i> (Meigen, 1818)		1147	escan									•			
<i>Chionea (Sphaeconophilus) lutescens</i> Lundstrom, 1907		2000	ean									•			
<i>Crypteria limnophiloides</i> Bergroth, 1913		1230-1390	ean									•			
<i>Neolimnophila carteri</i> (Tonnoir, 1921)		1700-2389	ean											•	
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) divisa</i> (Walker, 1848)		1700-2389	ean											•	
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) flavata</i> (Westhoff, 1882)		1700	wes											•	
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) griseipennis</i> Meigen, 1838	1000		e			♦	♦								
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) lutea</i> Meigen, 1804	1200-1700	1147-1876	wcp			♦	♦					•		•	
<i>Erioptera (Mesocophona) bivittata</i> (Loew, 1873)		2389	esca												
<i>Gonempeda flava</i> (Schummel, 1829)	1000		e			♦	♦								
<i>Scleroprocta balcanica</i> Stary, 1976	1230-1350	1147	Eb			♦	♦					•			
<i>Symplecta (Symplecta) hybrida</i> (Meigen, 1804)	900-1000	930-1000	ho			♦	♦				•	•			
* <i>Cheilotrichia (Cheilotrichia) meridiana</i> Mendl, 1974	450-650		nmt												
<i>Cheilotrichia (Empeda) staryi</i> Mendl, 1973	1900-2300	1230-1390	cse			♦	♦	♦				•			
<i>Eriocnopa symplectoidea</i> (Kuntze, 1914)	2100		hom												
<i>Eriocnopa trivialis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1900-2000	2389	eit												
<i>Hoplolabis (Parilisia) yezoana</i> (Alexander, 1924)		1180-1250	esca									•			
<i>Ilisia maculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	1000		eit			♦	♦								
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) aduncus</i> Stary, 1978	900-1000		nmt			♦	♦								
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) appendiculatus</i> (Staeger, 1840)	1950	1230-1390	wes				♦					•			
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) bifidus</i> Goetghebuer, 1920		1147	eit									•			
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) brevipennis</i> Bangert, 1947	900-1230		csee			♦	♦								
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) crassipygus</i> Meijere, 1918		1147-1250	e									•			
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) curvatus</i> Tonnoir, 1920	1230		e			♦	♦					•			
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) directidens</i> Stary, 1976	1230-2000	1147-1450	Ebg			♦	♦					•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Lipsothrix errans</i> (Walker, 1848)	1230-1350	1147	e			♦						•			
* <i>Lipsothrix nobilis</i> Loew, 1873	450-700		e, ? csean	♦											
<i>Lipsothrix remota</i> (Walker, 1848)	1230-1350	1147	e			♦						•			
<i>Antocha (Antocha) vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1810		ewca				♦								
<i>Antocha (Orimargula) alpigena</i> (Mik, 1883)	1230-2000	1147-1850	csean			♦	♦					•			
<i>Orimarga (Orimarga) attenuata</i> (Walker, 1848)	2000-2200		ena				♦								
<i>Orimarga (Orimarga) juvenilis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1851)	1000		e	♦		♦									
* <i>Achyrolimonia decemmaculata</i> (Loew, 1873)	1200		eswa			♦									
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) chorea</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1200-1700		h			♦	♦								
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) conchifera</i> (Strobl, 1901)	1230-1350		cse, ? e			♦									
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) luteipennis</i> Goetghebuer, 1920		1147-1475	cse									•			
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) mitis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1300-1900	1147-1850	wp			♦	♦					•			
* <i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) ornata</i> (Meigen, 1818)	300-1000		ean	♦								•			
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) signata</i> (Lacksehewitz, 1941)	1000		em	♦											
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) signata</i> (Lacksehewitz, 1941)	1300-1800		hoes			♦	♦								
<i>Dicranomyia (Melanolimonia) caledonica</i> Edwards, 1926	300-450		wp	♦											
* <i>Dicranomyia (Melanolimonia) morio</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	1900-2000		h				♦								
<i>Dicranomyia (Numantia) fusca</i> (Meigen, 1804)		1147-1250	hoa									•			
<i>Discobola annulata</i> (Linnaeus 1758)	1230-1810	1147	ena			♦	♦					•			
<i>Limonia flavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	1200		? eit			♦	♦								
<i>Limonia hercegovinae</i> (Strobl, 1898)	1200-1700	1147-1250	po			♦	♦					•			
<i>Limonia macrostigma</i> (Schummel, 1829)	1300-1800		e			♦	♦								
<i>Limonia nigropunctata</i> (Schummel, 1829)	2000		h				♦								
<i>Limonia nubeculosa</i> Meigen, 1804	1230-1350		cse			♦									
<i>Limonia pannonica</i> (Kowarz, 1868)	1230-1350	1147	wp			♦						•			
<i>Limonia phragmitidis</i> (Schränk, 1781)	1250-2300		e			♦	♦	♦							
<i>Limonia stigma</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1600-1700	1147-1850	wces			♦	♦					•			
<i>Limonia sylvicola</i> (Schummel, 1829)	1300-1800		ean			♦	♦								
<i>Limonia taurica</i> (Strobl, 1895)		1230-1390	esca									•			
<i>Limonia trivittata</i> (Schummel, 1829)		1876	hoes												
<i>Metalimnobia (Metalimnobia) zetterstedti</i> (Tjeder, 1968)	1230-1350	1174-1700	e			♦						•			
<i>Neolimonia dumetorum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	1200-1950	1147-1390	h			♦	♦					•			
<i>Rhipidia (Rhipidia) maculata</i> Meigen, 1818						♦	♦					•			
Pediciidae															
<i>Dicranota (Dicranota) bimaculata</i> (Schummel, 1829)	1230-1810	1876	wp												
<i>Dicranota (Ludicia) lucidipennis</i> (Edwards, 1921)		1174-1876	cse			♦	♦					•			
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) brevicornis</i> Bergroth, 1891		1876	cse									•			
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) flammifera</i> Stary, 1981		1147	cse									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>*Diceranota (Paradicranota) landrocki</i> Czizek, 1931	450-650	1876-2389	? wp, ? eit	♦											
<i>Diceranota (Paradicranota) pallens</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	450-700		csee	♦									•	•	
<i>*Diceranota (Paradicranota) schisacea</i> Lackschewitz, 1940		1147	csee	♦								•			
<i>Diceranota (Paradicranota) simulans</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	1230-1350		csea									•			
<i>Diceranota (Paradicranota) subtilis</i> Loew, 1871	1600-2000	1147-2389	e		♦							•	•	•	
<i>Pedicia (Amalopsis) occulta</i> (Meigen, 1830)		1147	eswa				♦					•			
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) littoralis</i> (Meigen, 1804)		1250	e									•			
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) riedeli</i> (Lackschewitz, 1940)	1750	1230-1390	cse				♦					•			
<i>Pedicia (Pedicia) rivosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1876	wes									•			
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) spinifera</i> Stary, 1974			Ebs										•		
<i>Tricyphona (Tricyphona) immaculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	1900-2200		? wp				♦								
<i>Tricyphona (Tricyphona) livida</i> Madarassy, 1881	2000	1230-1390	e				♦					•			
<i>*Tricyphona (Tricyphona) zwicki</i> Mendi, 1973	1200		se			♦									
<i>Ula (Ula) mollissima</i> Haliday 1833		1230-1390	ean									•			
BLEPHARICEROMORPHA															
Blephariceridae															
<i>Blepharicera fasciata</i> (Westwood, 1842)		1400	? cseit									•			
<i>Liponeura cinerascens</i> Loew, 1844		1230-2925	cscan									•	•	•	•
BIBIOMORPHA															
Bibionidae															
<i>Bibio hortulanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1147	wp									•			
<i>Bibio lanigerus</i> Meigen, 1818		550-2100	e							•		•	•		
<i>Bibio marci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		400	ena, ? wp							•					
<i>Bibio pomonae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		850-1000	des								•				
Mycetophiliidae															
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) cinerascens</i> (Macquart, 1826)	1740	1230-1390	ho				♦					•			
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) disa</i> Vaisanen, 1984		1450	e									•			
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) flavicollis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1852)	1740		e				♦								
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) marginata</i> (Meigen, 1818)	1740		po				♦								
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) prominens</i> (Lundström, 1913)		930-1000	e, ? wes									•			
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) ruficollis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1852)		1450	h									•			
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) tenuis</i> (Walker, 1856)	1740	1450	? h				♦					•			
<i>Mycomya (Mycomyopsis) trilineata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	1740		hoes				♦								
<i>Boletina gripha</i> Dziedziński, 1885		2389	hoes											•	
<i>Boletina plana</i> (Walker, 1856)	1740		hoes				♦								
<i>Boletina sciarina</i> Staeger, 1840	1740-1800	1000-1100	h				♦					•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Macroceridae															
<i>Macrocera centralis</i> Meigen, 1818	1700-1820	1350-1450	wes				♦					•			
<i>Macrocera grandis</i> Lundström, 1912		1150	cee									•			
<i>Macrocera inversa</i> Loew, 1869	1740	1300	wes				♦					•			
<i>Macrocera parva</i> Lundström, 1914	1740		wces				♦								
<i>Macrocera stigmoides</i> Edwards, 1925	1700-1820	1300	e				♦					•			
Sciariidae															
<i>Phytosciara (Phytosciara) halterata</i> (Lengersdorf, 1926)		1150	e									•			
<i>Phytosciara (Phytosciara) macrotricha</i> (Lengersdorf, 1926)		1150	cee									•			
<i>Sciara analis</i> Schiner, 1864		550-2100	csee, ? wes							•	•	•	•		
<i>Sciara hemerobioides</i> (Scopoli, 1763)		545-1150	po							•	•	•			
Cecidomyiidae															
<i>Lasioptera eryngii</i> (Vallot, 1829)	850	850-900	ena		♦						•				
<i>Lasioptera rubi</i> (Schrank, 1803)		800-1000	des								•				
<i>Bayertola capitigena</i> (Bremer, 1847)	850-1300	850-1150	e		♦		♦				•				
<i>Bayertola thymicola</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	850	400-900	ena		♦					•	•	•			
<i>Cystiphora taraxaci</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	980		e		♦										
<i>Dasineura acrophila</i> (Winnertz 1853)		850	h								•				
<i>Dasineura asperulae</i> (Löw, 1875)	850	850	cse, ? e		♦						•				
<i>Dasineura crataegi</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	350-850	800-1300	e		♦						•				
<i>Dasineura flicina</i> (Kieffer, 1889)	1500-2500		des, ? dp				♦	♦	♦						
<i>Dasineura fraxinea</i> Kieffer, 1907		850	e								•				
<i>Dasineura galitcola</i> (Löw, 1880)	1100	1150	e				♦					•			
<i>Dasineura hyperici</i> (Bremer, 1848)	850-1300	800-1150	e		♦		♦				•				
<i>Dasineura irregularis</i> (Bremer, 1847)		1200	cse, ? e									•			
<i>Dasineura medicaginis</i> (Bremer, 1847)		850	wes								•				
<i>Dasineura papaveris</i> (Winnertz, 1890)		400-850	csecan							•	•				
<i>Dasineura plicatrix</i> (Loew, 1850)	1100-1300	400	ena				♦			•					
<i>Dasineura potentillae</i> (Wachtl, 1885)	1300		e				♦								
<i>Dasineura pteridicola</i> (Kieffer 1901)		850	wes, ? e								•				
<i>Dasineura pyri</i> (Bouché 1847)		400	ha							•					
<i>Dasineura rosae</i> (Bremer, 1847)	850-1300	400-1200	dp, ? h		♦		♦			•	•	•			
<i>Dasineura rossi</i> Rübbsaamen, 1914		850	wes							•	•				
<i>Dasineura schulzei</i> (Rübbsaamen, 1917)	1100-1300	1150	csee, ? e				♦				•				

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Dasineura sisymbrii</i> (Schränk, 1803)	980-1000		e		◆	◆									
<i>Dasineura thomasi</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	980		e		◆	◆									
<i>Dasineura tortilis</i> (Bremi, 1847)	1000-1100	1150	e												
<i>Dasineura tortrix</i> (Löw, 1877)	1100-1300	400-1200	e							●	●	●			
<i>Dasineura trifolii</i> (Löw, 1874)	900-1100	900-1150	h		◆	◆					●	●			
<i>Dasineura ulmaria</i> (Bremi, 1847)	1000		des, ? dp												
<i>Dasineura urticae</i> (Perris, 1840)	980-1100	900-1150	des, ? dp		◆	◆				●	●	●			
<i>Euphorbomyia loewii</i> (Milk, 1882)		400	csec												
<i>Rabdophaga heterobia</i> (Loew, 1850)	1100-1300	1150	dp			◆						●			
<i>Rabdophaga saliciperda</i> (Dufour, 1841)	1300		dp, ? tp			◆									
<i>Rabdophaga salicis</i> (Schränk, 1803)	1300		h			◆									
<i>Rabdophaga terminalis</i> (Loew, 1850)	980-1300	1150	tp, ? dp		◆	◆						●			
<i>Dryomyia circinans</i> (Giraud, 1861)	450		dp	◆											
<i>Geocrypta galii</i> (Loew, 1850)	1100-1300	1100-1200	? des, ? dp			◆						●			
<i>Gephyraulus raphanistris</i> (Kieffer, 1886)		800	e								●				
<i>Hartigola annulipes</i> (Hartig, 1839)	+++	800-1200	dp								●	●			
<i>Iteomyia capreae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	1100	1150	tp			◆						●			
<i>Jaapiella bryoniae</i> (Bouche, 1847)	980-1000	900	ena		◆						●				
<i>Jaapiella cucubali</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	850		cse		◆										
<i>Jaapiella jaapiana</i> (Rübsaamen, 1914)		400	e							●					
<i>Jaapiella veronicae</i> (Vallot, 1827)	1100	800-1200	e			◆					●	●			
<i>Fabomya medicaginis</i> (Rübsaamen, 1912)	850		wes, wesc		◆										
<i>Janetiella fallax</i> Kieffer, 1904		850-900	e								●				
<i>Janetiella lemezi</i> (Kieffer, 1904)		400	ean							●					
<i>Janetiella thymi</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	1100-1300	1150	e			◆						●			
<i>Macrolabis heraclei</i> Kaltenbach, 1862	980	1150	e		◆							●			
<i>Macrolabis lamii</i> Rübsaamen, 1916	980		e		◆										
<i>Macrolabis stallariae</i> (Liebel, 1889)	980		e		◆										
<i>Manetiella poae</i> (Bosc, 1817)		+++	e												
<i>Phegomyia fagicola</i> (Kieffer, 1901)	1100		e			◆						●			
<i>Physemocelis ulmi</i> (Kieffer, 1909)		1150	e			◆						●			
<i>Mikiola fagi</i> (Hartig, 1839)	1100	400-1150	e							●	●	●			
<i>Mikiola orientalis</i> Kieffer 1909		800-1200	e, ? des			◆					●	●			
<i>Mikomyia coryli</i> (Kieffer, 1901)		1230-1400	ban								●	●			
<i>Oligotrophus juniperinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	850-1300	850-1150	ean								●	●			
		850-2500	e		◆	◆					●	●		●	

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Psychoptera (Psychoptera) scutellaris</i> Meigen, 1818		2100	h										•		
CULICOMORPHA															
Culicidae															
<i>Anopheles (Anopheles) maculipennis</i> Meigen, 1818		2190-2200	hoes, ? tp									•	•		
<i>Culiseta (Culiseta) annulata</i> (Schränk, 1776)		1230-1390	ena								•				
<i>Culiseta (Culiseta) glaphyoptera</i> (Schiner, 1864)		1230-1390	csec, m								•				
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) communis</i> (De Geer, 1776)		1230-1390	h								•				
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) pullatus</i> (Coquillett, 1904)		1230-2300	h, ba								•				
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) punctor</i> (Kirby, 1837)		1230-1390	h								•				
<i>Ochlerotatus (Finlaya) geniculatus</i> (Olivier, 1791)		1230-1390	wp, ? tp								•				
<i>Culex (Culex) pipiens</i> Linnaeus, 1758		550-2100	hnat							•			•		
<i>Culex (Mailloita) hortensis</i> Ficalbi 1889		1230-1390	wpo								•				
Simuliidae															
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) fulvipes</i> (Edwards, 1921)		1300-2400	cseca, des									•	•		
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) hirtipes</i> (Fries, 1824)		1300-2450	tp, ? h									•	•		
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) latimicro</i> (Enderlein, 1925)		1200-2400	e									•	•		
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) petrosum</i> Rubtsov, 1955		1100-2235	see									•	•		
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) rufipes</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1200-1400	1300-2300	ena			♦						•	•		
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) tomosvaryi</i> (Enderlein, 1921)		850-2000	des									•	•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) angustitarse</i> (Lundstrom 1911)		1000-1700	wcp, ? dp									•	•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) berrandi</i> Grenier et Dorier, 1959	1950	1950-2300	e				♦						•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) brevidens</i> (Rubtsov, 1956)		450-2350	e							•			•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) carpathicum</i> (Knoz, 1961)	2000	400-2000	e				♦						•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) carhusiense</i> Grenier & Dorier, 1959		1000-2300	e										•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) codreanu</i> (Serban, 1958)	1950	1300-2150	e				♦						•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) costatum</i> Friederichs, 1920		1100-2300	ena										•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) crenobium</i> (Knoz, 1961)		1400	csee										•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) cryophilum</i> (Rubzov, 1959)	700-750	750-2200	eanna, ? tp								•		•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) curvans</i> (Rubtsov & Carlsson, 1965)		1200-2100	hoes										•		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) latigonia</i> (Rubzov, 1956)		1100-2000	e										•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) argenteostriatum</i> Strobl, 1898	700-1300	700-2100	? csena			♦							•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) argyreatum</i> Meigen, 1838		400-2400	e										•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) bezzii</i> (Corti, 1914)		1200-2200	ena, mwca										•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) degranet</i> Dorier et Grenier, 1959	700	700-2200	cse			♦							•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) ibariense</i> Zivkovich & Grenier, 1959		868	csee										•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) maximum</i> Knoz, 1961	450	450-2200	e, cse			♦							•		

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Simulium (Simulium) monticola</i> Friederichs, 1920		600-2200	ena							•	•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) morsitans</i> Edwards, 1915		1400-2000	des								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) noelleri</i> Friederichs, 1920		800-1800	wces								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) colombaschense</i> (Scopoli, 1780)		1800-2250	cse								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) ornatum</i> (Meigen, 1818)		780-960	tp, ? e								•				
<i>Simulium (Simulium) reptans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		800-2000	hoes, h								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) tuberosum</i> (Lundstrom, 1911)		500-2300	h								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) variegatum</i> Meigen, 1818		400-2300	e, ? wp							•	•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Simulium) verecundum</i> Stone & Jamnback, 1955		1000-2000	h, bm								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Hellichiella) latipes</i> Meigen, 1804	2060	900-2200	tp, ? h			♦					•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) angustipes</i> Edwards, 1915	2240	900-2240	wp				♦				•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) aureum</i> Fries, 1824		700-2000	wes, ? h								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) velutinum</i> (Santos Abreu, 1922)		1000-2000	ena								•	•	•		
<i>Simulium (Obuchovia) auricoma</i> Meigen, 1818		1000-2400	ena ? dp								•	•	•		
Ceratopogonidae															
<i>Culicoides (Avaritia) obsoletus</i> (Meigen, 1818)		1230-1390	h									•			
<i>Culicoides festivi-pennis</i> Kieffer, 1914		+++	tp												
<i>Culicoides (Silvaticulicoides) pallidicornis</i> Kieffer, 1919		1230-1390	tp									•			
<i>Culicoides pictipennis</i> (Staeger, 1839)		2400-2900	wcp											•	•
<i>Dasyhelea (Dasyhelea) bilineata</i> Goetghebuer 1920	2090-2190		? tp				♦								
<i>Dasyhelea (Dasyhelea) flavifrons</i> (Guerin, 1833)		2200	tp, ? hoes										•	•	
<i>Forcipomyia (Forcipomyia) pallidipes</i> Santos Abreu, 1918		1230-1390	mwca									•			
Chironomidae															
<i>Anatopynia plumipes</i> (Fries, 1823)		2283-2340	e											•	
<i>Guttipetopia guttipennis</i> (Wulp, 1861)		2250-2324	h											•	
<i>Larsia curticalcar</i> (Kieffer, 1918)	2020-2365	800-2440	e				♦				•	•	•	•	
<i>Trissopelopia flavida</i> Kieffer, 1923		340-900	et							•	•				
<i>Zavrelimyia melanura</i> (Meigen, 1804)		1070-1850	tp									•	•		
<i>Diamesa (Diamesa) insignipes</i> Kieffer, 1908		1500-2440	h									•	•	•	
<i>Pothastia gaedii</i> (Meigen, 1838)		1070-1850	ho									•	•		
<i>Pseudodiamesa (Pseudodiamesa) branickii</i> (Nawicki, 1873)	1140-1950		ho			♦									
<i>Pseudodiamesa (Pseudodiamesa) nivosa</i> (Goetghebuer, 1928)		1040	wcp									•			
<i>Prodiamesa olivacea</i> (Meigen, 1818)		1040-2196	h									•	•		
<i>Acricotopus lucens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1850)	1140-1950	1140-1950	h				♦					•	•		
<i>Brillia bifida</i> (Kieffer, 1909)		1040-2535	po									•	•	•	•
<i>Corynoneura celeripes</i> Winnertz, 1852		2178	h									•	•	•	•

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) algarum</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	2020-2394	400-2394	e, ? wes				◆	◆		•	•	•	•	•	
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) annulator</i> Goetghebuer, 1927	2365	480-2030	h					◆		•	•	•	•	•	
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) fuscus</i> (Kieffer, 1909)		340	h							•					
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) tremulus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		2250	h							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Cricotopus (Isocladius) sylvestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	2020-2365	370-2535	hno				◆	◆		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Eukiefferiella breviculcar</i> (Kieffer, 1911)		1568	wp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Eukiefferiella clypeata</i> (Thienemann, 1919)		1550	wp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Eukiefferiella graeci</i> (Edwards, 1929)		1170-1200	h								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Eukiefferiella similis</i> Goetghebuer, 1939		900-2350	tp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Linnophyes minimus</i> (Meigen, 1818)		860-900	hptn								•	•	•	•	•
? <i>Orthocladus murvanidzei</i> (Chernovskij, 1949)		2250-2440	wces								•	•	•	•	•
? <i>Paracladius inaequalis</i> Kieffer, 1926		800-1200	? e								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Psectrocladius (Psectrocladius) psilopterus</i> (Kieffer, 1906)		2250-2324	h								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Psectrocladius (Psectrocladius) simulans</i> (Johannsen, 1937)		2228-2324	h								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Rheocricotopus (Rheocricotopus) effusus</i> (Walker, 1856)	1140-1950	850-1150	ho			◆	◆			•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Synorthocladus semivirens</i> (Kieffer, 1909)		980-2250	h							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Thienemannia gracilis</i> Kieffer, 1909		1070-1850	e							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Thienemanniella acuticornis</i> (Kieffer, 1912)		512	wp							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Thienemanniella flaviforceps</i> Kieffer, 1925		350-1850	e							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tvetenia bavarica</i> (Goetghebuer, 1934)		480	h							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tvetenia cabrescens</i> (Edwards, 1929)		400-2250	wp							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Zalutschia mucronata</i> (Brundin, 1949)		350-1000	wes							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Chironomus (Lobochironomus) dorsalis</i> Meigen, 1818		2353-2535	h								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) plumosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2020-2394	2250-2324	hno				◆	◆		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) riparius</i> Meigen, 1804	2020-2365	400-2535	hn				◆	◆		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Cryptochironomus (Cryptochironomus) defectus</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	2020-2394	2020-2545	pa				◆	◆		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Orthocladus (Eudaclyocladius) fuscimanus</i> (Kieffer, 1908)		800-1000	wp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Demicryptochironomus (Demicryptochironomus) vulneratus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)		1568-2228	po								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Dicrotendipes nervosus</i> (Staeger, 1839)		1568-2440	ho								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Einfieldia longipes</i> (Staeger, 1839)		2324-2440	h								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Endochironomus dispar</i> (Meigen, 1830)		800-1000	hes								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Glyptotendipes (Glyptotendipes) pallens</i> (Meigen, 1804)		1550-1568	po								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Paratendipes nudisquama</i> (Edwards, 1929)		440-1140	hno							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Polypedium (Pentapedium) exsectum</i> (Kieffer, 1916)		2200	des								•	•	•	•	•

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Rhagio conspicuus</i> Meigen, 1804	1700-1800	550-1800	e			♦				•	•	•	•		
<i>Rhagio lineola</i> Fabricius, 1794	1000-1100		des			♦									
<i>Rhagio scolopaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1000	1150	wes			♦				•					
<i>Rhagio tringarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	350-450	550	wes	♦						•					
<i>Rhagio vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1820)	1000		e			♦									
Tabanidae															
<i>Nemotus vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1820)		+++	cseit							•					
<i>Chrysops (Chrysops) caecutiens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		400-900	hoes, ? tp								•				
<i>Chrysops (Petersenichrysops) hamatus</i> Loew, 1858	300-400		ban	♦											
<i>Alyotus fulvus</i> (Meigen, 1804)		900-2550	tp							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra aterrima</i> (Meigen, 1820)	1500	900-2654	cse, m			♦				•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra auripila</i> (Meigen, 1820)	1500	900-2550	e			♦				•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra cureati</i> (Séguy, 1937)		1200-1800	esca								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra distinguenda</i> (Verrall, 1909)		1800	hoes, ? tp												
<i>Hybomitra micans</i> (Meigen, 1804)		1150-2100	e									•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra montana</i> (Meigen, 1820)		900-1390	hoes, ? tp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hybomitra tropica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		900-1390	e								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus bovinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758		1200-1800	tp, ? hop								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus bromius</i> Linnaeus, 1758		550-1800	wp							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus cordiger</i> Meigen, 1820		1200-1800	wp								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus glaucopsis</i> Meigen, 1820		550-1800	esca							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus maculicornis</i> Zetterstedt, 1842		1200-1600	wes							•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus miki</i> Brauer, 1880		900-1600	eit								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus quatuornotatus</i> Meigen, 1820		1200	wp									•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus spodopterus</i> Meigen, 1820	1000	1200-2550	? csean			♦						•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus tergostinus</i> Egger, 1859		1200-1600	eit									•	•	•	•
<i>Tabanus unifasciatus</i> Loew, 1858		1200-1600	? wp									•	•	•	•
<i>Haematopota grandis</i> Meigen, 1820		1200-1400	wp									•	•	•	•
<i>Haematopota italica</i> Meigen, 1804		+++	eama												
<i>Haematopota pluvialis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1600	wcp									•	•	•	•
<i>Philipomyia aprica</i> (Meigen, 1820)	+++	900-1400	eit, ? cseit								•	•	•	•	•
<i>Philipomyia graeca</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		900-2000	csea								•	•	•	•	•
Acroceridae															
<i>Ogcodes (Ogcodes) lautereri</i> Chvala, 1980	2000-2500		hom, ? mm				♦								
Bombyliidae															

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Neotamus colturnatus</i> (Meigen, 1820)		+++	e												
<i>Neotamus cyanurus</i> (Loew, 1849)		1200-1450	hoes									•			
<i>Neotamus impudicus</i> (Gerstaecker, 1862)	1000		Eb		♦	♦									
<i>Philonicus albiceps</i> (Meigen, 1820)	1000		tp		♦	♦									
<i>Neomochtherus geniculatus</i> (Meigen, 1820)		+++	e, ? cse												
<i>Stilpnogaster aemula</i> (Meigen, 1820)		850-1300	e								•	•			
<i>Tolmerus atricapillus</i> (Fallen, 1814)		1200-1400	hoes, ? tp									•			
<i>Tolmerus bolgaricus</i> Lehr, 1981		1000-1100	Ebg									•			
Empididae															
<i>Hilara discoidalis</i> Lundbeck, 1910	2500		e				♦	♦							
<i>Hilara setipes</i> Straka, 1976	1230-1900		Ebg			♦	♦								
<i>Empis (Empis) ciliata</i> Fabricius, 1787		1200	des									•			
<i>Empis (Empis) prodromus</i> Loew, 1867	900-1000		e		♦										
<i>Empis (Euempis) tessellata</i> Fabricius, 1794		545-2100	hop							•	•	•	•		
<i>Empis (Polyblepharis) opaca</i> Meigen, 1804		+++	e												
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) morio</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	1950-2230		e				♦	♦							
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) sulcata</i> (Meigen, 1804)		+++	hoes												
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) tibialis</i> Meigen, 1822		1200	des									•			
<i>Rhamphomyia (Pararhamphomyia) simplex</i> (Zetterstedt, 1849)	1810		e				♦	♦							
<i>Rhamphomyia (Holoclera) culticna</i> (Fallen, 1816)		+++	e												
<i>Rhamphomyia (Holoclera) trigemina</i> Oldenberg, 1927	1810		e				♦	♦							
<i>Phaeobalia dimidiata</i> (Loew, 1869)	+++		e, ? cse												
<i>Chelifera precabunda</i> Collin, 1961		+++	? e												
<i>Wiedemannia (Chamaedipsia) lota</i> Walker, 1851		+++	eswa												
Hybotidae															
<i>Bicellaria nigra</i> (Meigen, 1824)		930-1000	e								•	•			
<i>Platypalpus maculipes</i> (Meigen, 1829)	+++	930-1000	e								•	•			
<i>Platypalpus niger</i> (Meigen, 1804)		930-1000	e								•	•			
<i>Platypalpus nigrirtarsis</i> (Fallen, 1816)	+++		e												
<i>Platypalpus pallidicornis</i> (Collin, 1926)		930-1000	e								•	•			
<i>Crossopalpus humilis</i> (Frey, 1913)	+++		wces												
<i>Drapetis (Drapetis) assimilis</i> (Fallen, 1815)		930-1000	e, ? h								•	•			
Dolichopodidae															
<i>Rhaphium crassipes</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1374-1400	wes									•			
<i>Rhaphium monotrichum</i> Loew, 1850		1374-1400	wces									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Triphleba bicornuta</i> (Strobl, 1910)		2000-2100	e										•		
Syrphidae															
<i>Dasyrhyphus albostrigatus</i> (Fallén, 1817)		1200-1400	tp									•			
<i>Dasyrhyphus venustus</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1200-2000	h									•	•		
<i>Didea alneti</i> (Fallén, 1817)		2925	h												•
<i>Doros profuges</i> (Harris 1780)		1200-1400	hoes									•			
<i>Epistrophe diaphana</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)		1200-1400	esca									•			
<i>Epistrophe eligans</i> (Harris, 1780)	1000	1200-1400	et	♦								•			
<i>Epistrophe grossulariae</i> (Meigen, 1822)		+++	h												
<i>Epistrophe nitidicollis</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1200-1400	h									•			
<i>Epistrophella euchroma</i> (Kowarz, 1885)		1500-1550	hoes									•			
<i>Episyphus balteatus</i> (De Geer, 1776)		1147	poa									•			
<i>Leucozona lucorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1500-2300	h									•	•		
<i>Melangyna lasiophthalma</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)		1800	esca										•		
<i>Meligrama guttata</i> (Fallén, 1817)		1200-1400	h									•			
<i>Meligrama triangulifera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)		1200-1400	h									•			
<i>Melisaeva auricollis</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1200-1400	wp									•			
<i>Melisaeva cinctella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	+++	1170-1200	ho									•			
<i>Eupeodes lapponicus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	+++	1200-1400	h									•			
<i>Eupeodes corollae</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	300-1000	900-1550	ppta	♦								•			
<i>Eupeodes latifasciatus</i> (Macquart, 1829)		1147	ho									•			
<i>Eupeodes luniger</i> (Meigen, 1822)	1000	1200-1400	ho	♦								•			
<i>Eupeodes nitens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	1500	400-1374	tp	♦								•			
<i>Parasyrphus lineolus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	1500	1200-1800	h							•		•			
<i>Parasyrphus malinellus</i> (Collin, 1952)	1500	1800	des											•	
<i>Scavea pyrastris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1200-1400	ho	♦								•			
<i>Sphaerophoria menthastris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1000	1200-1400	hop									•			
<i>Sphaerophoria philanthea</i> (Meigen, 1822)		550-650	h							•					
<i>Sphaerophoria scripta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1000	550-1900	ho	♦						•		•			
<i>Syrphus ribesii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1000-1500	800-1100	h	♦						•		•			
<i>Syrphus torvus</i> Osten-Sacken, 1875	1500	800-1000	ho	♦						•		•			
<i>Syrphus vitripennis</i> Meigen, 1822	1500	800-1000	ho	♦						•		•			
<i>Xanthogramma pedissequum</i> (Harris, 1776)		1500-1550	tp									•			

Table 2. Continued

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Baccha elongata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		+++	1147	h									•			
<i>Chrysotoxum arcuatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			400-1550	tp							•		•			
<i>Chrysotoxum elegans</i> Loew, 1841			1200-1550	e									•			
<i>Chrysotoxum fasciolatum</i> (De Geer, 1776)			1200-1550	h									•			
<i>Chrysotoxum festivum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1500	450-1147	po			♦				•		•			
<i>Chrysotoxum intermedium</i> (Meigen, 1822)			1500-1550	wp									•			
<i>Chrysotoxum octomaculatum</i> Curtis, 1837			1200-1400	wes									•			
<i>Chrysotoxum vernale</i> Loew, 1841		1500	350-450	esca			♦				•		•			
<i>Melanostoma mellinum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		300-1800	540-2100	h	♦		♦				•		•			
<i>Xanthandrus comtus</i> (Harris, 1780)			1200-1550	po									•			
<i>Platycheirus ambiguus</i> (Fallén, 1817)			1200-1400	ho									•			
<i>Platycheirus albimanus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)		1500	1800	ho			♦						•			
<i>Platycheirus clypeatus</i> (Fabricius, 1822)			1147	h									•			
<i>Platycheirus fulviventris</i> (Macquart, 1829)			1200-1400	esca									•			
<i>Platycheirus manicatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)			900-1400	h								•	•			
<i>Platycheirus melanops</i> Loew, 1856			1800	des									•			
<i>Platycheirus peltatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)			1147-1550	h									•			
<i>Platycheirus podagratus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)			900	h								•				
<i>Platycheirus scutatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)		+++	1170-1400	h									•			
<i>Paragus albifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)			1147	tp									•			
<i>Paragus bicolor</i> (Fabricius, 1794)			400-1374	h							•		•			
<i>Paragus cinctus</i> Schiner & Egger, 1853				? mt									•			
<i>Paragus haemorrhous</i> Meigen, 1822			1200-1400	hat									•			
<i>Paragus quadrifasciatus</i> Meigen, 1822			1500-1550	tp									•			
<i>Paragus tibialis</i> (Fallén, 1817)		+++	400-1400	ho							•		•			
<i>Heringia pubescens</i> (Delucchi & Pechorn-Walcher, 1955)		+++		h									•			
<i>Pipiza austriaca</i> Meigen, 1822			1374-1400	hoes									•			
<i>Pipiza quadrimaculata</i> (Panzer, 1804)			+++	h									•			
<i>Pipizella virens</i> (Fabricius, 1805)		1800	900-1200	tp			♦						•			
<i>Trichopsonyia flavitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)			900	hoes									•			
<i>Triglyphus primus</i> Loew, 1840			1500-1550	hoes, ? tp									•			
<i>Chamaesyphus scaevoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)		1810	1200	des			♦						•			
<i>Cheilosia albitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1500	1200-1800	h			♦						•			
<i>Cheilosia antiqua</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1800		e, ? ese			♦						•			
<i>Cheilosia barbata</i> Loew, 1857			900	e								•				

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Cheilosis bureschi</i> (Delkeskamp, 1942)	900-1000		Ebg		◆										
<i>Cheilosis canicularis</i> (Panzer, 1801)		900-1400	hoes								●				
<i>Cheilosis carbonaria</i> Egger, 1860	1500		wces			◆									
<i>Cheilosis flavipes</i> (Panzer, 1798)	1500		wces			◆									
<i>Cheilosis frontalis</i> Loew, 1857	900-1000		e		◆										
<i>Cheilosis gagatea</i> Loew, 1857	1200-1400		cse			◆									
<i>Cheilosis illustrata</i> (Harris, 1780)		1200-1550	hoes								●				
<i>Cheilosis impressa</i> Loew, 1840	900-1000	1200-1800	hoes		◆						●		●		
<i>Cheilosis latifrons</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)		1200-1400	wp				◆				●				
<i>Cheilosis melanopa</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)		400-1550	e							●	●				
<i>Cheilosis melanura</i> (Becker, 1894)		1800	des											●	
<i>Cheilosis montana</i> Egger, 1860	1500		wes			◆									
<i>Cheilosis morio</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)		400-1550	wces							●	●				
<i>Cheilosis mutabilis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	1500-2000	1200-1400	wcp			◆					●				
<i>Cheilosis nebulosa</i> (Verrall, 1871)	1800		e				◆								
<i>Cheilosis pagana</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1500-1550	h								●				
<i>Cheilosis pallipes</i> Loew, 1863		1500-1550	h								●				
<i>Cheilosis proxima</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	+++	1150-1400	hoes												
<i>Cheilosis pubera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	1800	1800	e				◆							●	
<i>Cheilosis rhynchops</i> Egger, 1860		1800	e											●	
<i>Cheilosis ruralis</i> (Meigen, 1822) [<i>Ch. urbana</i> (Meigen, 1822)]	300-1800	1150	hoes, ? tp		◆	◆	◆					●			
<i>Cheilosis sahlbergi</i> Becker, 1894	1810		e				◆								
<i>Cheilosis schineri</i> Egger, 1860		1500-1550	se									●			
<i>Cheilosis semifasciata</i> (Becker, 1894)		+++	e												
<i>Cheilosis variabilis</i> (Panzer, 1798)	1500	1350-1475	wcp			◆						●			
<i>Cheilosis velutina</i> Loew, 1840	+++	400-1000	hoes							●	●				
<i>Cheilosis vernalis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	1800	1200-1400	hoes				◆					●			
<i>Cheilosis vulpina</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1200-1400	e									●			
<i>Ferdinandea cuprea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)		1200-1400	tp									●			
<i>Peleocera tricineta</i> Meigen, 1822		1200-1400	des									●			
<i>Rhingia campestris</i> Meigen, 1822		1350-1475	hoes									●			
<i>Rhingia rostrata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1200-1400	wes									●			
<i>Volucella bombylans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1150-2500	h									●		●	
<i>Volucella inanis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1150-2000	esca									●		●	
<i>Volucella pellucens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		+++	po												
<i>Volucella zonaria</i> (Poda, 1761)		1150-1400	tp									●			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Brachyopa bicolor</i> (Fallén, 1817)		1500-1550	? hoes									•			
<i>Brachyopa panzeri</i> Goffe, 1945		1147	des									•			
<i>Melanogaster parumplicata</i> (Loew, 1840)		1200-1400	? hoes									•			
<i>Chrysogaster solstitialis</i> (Fallén, 1817)		900-1400	ena								•	•			
<i>Pipizella viduata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1000-1500	550-1800	e			♦				•	•	•			
<i>Lejogaster metallina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	1000-1500	1200-1400	tp			♦						•			
<i>Lejogaster tarsata</i> (Meigen, 1822)	300-400	900-1550	esca, ? tp	♦							•	•			
<i>Orthonевра elegans</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1200-1400	hoes									•			
<i>Orthonевра geniculata</i> (Meigen 1830)		1500-1550	hoes									•			
<i>Orthonевра nobilis</i> (Fallén, 1817)		1170-1400	esca									•			
<i>Neoscia annexa</i> (Müller, 1776)		+++	e												
<i>Neoscia podagrica</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		550-650	wcp							•					
<i>Neoscia metictulosa</i> (Scopoli, 1763)		1800	hoes, ? esca									•			
<i>Neoscia geniculata</i> (Meigen, 1822)		1800	wces									•			
<i>Sphagina clunipes</i> (Fallén, 1816)		1200-1800	des									•			
<i>Sphagina montana</i> Becker, 1921		1200-1400	e									•			
<i>Arctophila bequaerti</i> Herve-Bazin, 1913		900-1000	ban								•	•			
<i>Arctophila bombiforme</i> (Fallén, 1810)		1150-2145	e									•			
<i>Sericomyia lappona</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1800	hoes												
<i>Sericomyia silentis</i> (Harris, 1776)		1150-1400	hoes									•			
<i>Eumerus strigatus</i> (Fallén, 1817)		800-1500	ha, ? i								•	•			
<i>Merodon aberrans</i> Egger, 1860		1150	ena									•			
<i>Merodon aeneus</i> Meigen, 1822		1150-1400	ena									•			
<i>Merodon avidus</i> (Rossi, 1790)		1150-1400	ena									•			
<i>Merodon cinereus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		+++	cse												
<i>Merodon clavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)		1500-1550	ena									•			
<i>Merodon equestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		+++	ha												
<i>Merodon loewi</i> van der Goot, 1964		1500-1550	? e									•			
<i>Merodon ruficornis</i> Meigen, 1822	300-400	800-1800	ena	♦								•			
<i>Merodon rufus</i> Meigen, 1838		+++	ena												
<i>Merodon testaceus</i> Sack, 1913		1500-1550	nm									•			
<i>Psilota anthracina</i> Meigen, 1822		400-1550	e									•			
<i>Psarus abdominalis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		1500-1550	e							•		•			
<i>Ceriana conopsoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		1200-1400	tp									•			
<i>Eristalinus aeneus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)		350-400	hpta, ? sk							•					

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Dorylomyia (Dorylomyia) incognita</i> (Verrall, 1901)	1900-2000	930-1700	e			♦	♦								
<i>Tomosvaryella coquillei</i> (Kertész, 1907)	400-1900	360	ho	♦	♦	♦	♦			•					
<i>Tomosvaryella geniculata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-400	1350-1475	e	♦								•			
<i>Tomosvaryella kuthyi</i> (Aezél, 1944)	400-950		ean	♦	♦										
<i>Tomosvaryella nutata</i> (Becker, 1898)	650		hom	♦											
<i>Tomosvaryella sylvatica</i> (Meigen, 1824)	450-2350		ho	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦							
SCHIZOPHORA															
ACALYPTRATA															
Conopidae															
<i>Conops (Asiconops) elegans</i> Meigen, 1824		900	hom								•				
<i>Conops (Conops) quadrijasciatus</i> De Geer, 1776		1200-1400	esanca									•			
<i>Conops (Conops) scutellatus</i> Meigen 1804		1150-1550	e									•			
<i>Conops (Conops) silaceus</i> Wiedemann in Meigen, 1824		1500-1550	se									•			
<i>Conops (Conops) vesicularis</i> Linnaeus, 1761		1150	tp									•			
<i>Conops (Conops) vitellinus</i> Loew, 1847		400-450	nm							•					
<i>Physocephala chrysothoea</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1200-1400	tp, ? hop									•			
<i>Physocephala nigra</i> (De Geer, 1776)		900	tp, ? hop								•				
<i>Physocephala pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-400		wcp	♦											
<i>Physocephala variegata</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1200-1400	sp									•			
<i>Zodion cinereum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		1150-1500	po									•			
<i>Zodion erythrurum</i> Rondani, 1865		1200-1400	sp, ? tp									•			
<i>Zodion notatum</i> (Meigen, 1804)		800-1200	hop									•			
<i>Myopa buccata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1800	1150-1800	tp									•			
<i>Myopa dorsalis</i> Fabricius, 1794		1200-1400	wpo									•			
<i>Myopa testacea</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)		800-1700	ho									•			
<i>Melanosoma bicolor</i> (Meigen 1824)		1200	wp									•			
<i>Myopotta pallipes</i> (Wiedemann in Meigen, 1824)		400	wesanca							•					
<i>Thecophora atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)		1150	po									•			
<i>Thecophora pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1000-1400	hop									•			
<i>Sicus ferrugineus</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)		1150-1700	po									•			
Tephritidae															
<i>Acidia cognata</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)		1150-1300	e									•			
<i>Euleta heraclei</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		2200	wp									•			
<i>Terellia (Terellia) colon</i> (Meigen 1826)		1200	wp									•			
<i>Acitura coryli</i> (Rossi, 1790)	900-1000		mwca									♦			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Oxya flavipennis</i> (Loew, 1844)		1200-1400	wccs									•			
<i>Oxya nebulosa</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	1800		eswa				♦					•			
<i>Tephritis bardanae</i> (Schrank, 1803)		1150-1300	wes									•			
<i>Tephritis vespertina</i> (Loew, 1844)		1200-1400	ena									•			
<i>Trypeta artemisiae</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		1150	ess									•			
<i>Stenomocera cornuta</i> (Scopoli, 1763)		1150-1300	wccs									•			
Piophilidae															
<i>Liopiophila varipes</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1800		h				♦								
Lauxaniidae															
<i>Calliopus aeneum</i> (Fallén, 1820)		900	e								•				
Cremifaniidae															
<i>Cremifania bulgarica</i> L. Papp, 2010		2250	Er											•	
Chamaemyiidae															
<i>Parochthiphilla (Eustelia) coronata</i> (Loew, 1858)	350-2350		tp	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦							
<i>Chamaemyia aestiva</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	1800-2200		tp				♦								
<i>Chamaemyia aridella</i> (Fallén, 1823)	300-2200		e	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Chamaemyia bicolor</i> Bheschovski, 1994	+++		Ebg												
<i>Chamaemyia junctorum</i> (Fallén, 1823)	350-2200		tp, ? hop	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Chamaemyia poly stigma</i> (Meigen, 1830)	350-650		tp, ? hop	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Chamaemyia subjunctorum</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	600-1000	2500	dp, ? tp	♦	♦	♦	♦							•	•
<i>Leucopsis (Leucopsis) aphidiperda</i> Rondani, 1847	300-650		esca	♦											
<i>Leucopsis (Leucopsis) attritarsis</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1958	350-450		h	♦											
<i>Leucopsis (Leucopsis) glyphinivora</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1958	350-700		ho	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Leucopsis (Leucopsis) pseudomelanopus</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1961	350-450		esca	♦											
<i>Leucopsis (Leucopsis) revisenda</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	350-450		esca	♦											
Sciomyzidae															
<i>Pherbellia cinerella</i> (Fallén, 1820)		900	wpo								•				
<i>Tetanocera ferruginea</i> Fallén, 1820		1150-1300	h									•			
Sepsidae															
<i>Sepsis fulgens</i> Meigen, 1826	1800		tp				♦								
Agromyzidae															
<i>Agromyza alnibetulae</i> Hendel, 1931		1150-1300	e									•			
<i>Agromyza lithospermi</i> Spencer, 1963	900-1000		e				♦								
<i>Agromyza nama</i> Meigen 1830		1374	wpo									•			
<i>Agromyza pseudoreptans</i> Nowakowski, 1967		1374	h									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Agromyza reptans</i> Fallen, 1823	900-1000	1700	ho		◆								•		
<i>Agromyza rufipes</i> Meigen, 1830		1700	wpo										•		
<i>Ophiomyia heringi</i> Stary, 1930		1150-1300	e									•			
<i>Ophiomyia labiatarum</i> Hering, 1937		1150-1300	h									•			
<i>Ophiomyia maura</i> (Meigen, 1838)		1150-1300	h									•			
<i>Amauromyza (Amauromyza) lamii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1858)		1700	e										•		
<i>Amauromyza (Amauromyza) mortionella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	900-1000	1300	ena		◆							•			
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) flavifrons</i> (Meigen, 1830)		580-1150	h							•		•			
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) gyrans</i> (Fallen 1823)		1150-1200	e									•			
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) labiatarum</i> (Hendel, 1920)	900-1000	1150-1200	e		◆							•			
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) verbasci</i> (Bouché, 1847)		1150-1200	e									•			
<i>Cerodontha (Poemyza) pygmaea</i> (Meigen 1830)		1374	h									•			
<i>Liriomyza amoena</i> (Meigen, 1830)		580	wpo							•					
<i>Liriomyza artemisicola</i> de Meijere, 1924		1150-1200	wpo							•					
<i>Liriomyza bulhri</i> Hering, 1937		580-660	e							•					
<i>Liriomyza congesta</i> (Becker, 1903)		580-1374	po							•					
<i>Liriomyza demeijerei</i> Hering, 1930		1150-1200	e							•					
<i>Liriomyza eupatorii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1873)	900-1000	1150-1200	h		◆							•			
<i>Liriomyza pascuum</i> (Meigen, 1838)		1374	e									•			
<i>Liriomyza puella</i> (Meigen, 1830)		1150-1200	e									•			
<i>Liriomyza sonchi</i> Hendel, 1931		580-1200	ho							•		•			
<i>Liriomyza strigata</i> (Meigen, 1830)		580-1200	po							•		•			
<i>Liriomyza taraxaci</i> Hering, 1927		1150-1374	h									•			
<i>Phytoliriomyza melampyga</i> (Loew, 1869)		1150-1200	h									•			
<i>Phytoliriomyza variegata</i> (Meigen, 1830)		580-1200	po							•		•			
<i>Calycomyza artemisiae</i> (Kaltenbach, 1856)		1150-1200	hno									•			
<i>Aulagromyza similis</i> (Brischke, 1880)		1150-1200	e							•		•			
<i>Aulagromyza tridentata</i> (Loew, 1858)		580-1200	ewca, ? eca							•		•			
<i>Pseudonapomyza europaea</i> Spencer, 1973	1800		h										◆		
<i>Phytomyza affinis</i> Fallén, 1823		580-660	e, ? h							•			◆		
<i>Phytomyza alpina</i> Groschke, 1957	2000	1374	e, ? h												
<i>Phytomyza artemisivora</i> Spencer, 1971	900-1000	1150-1200	ewca		◆							•			
<i>Phytomyza chaerophylli</i> (Kaltenbach, 1856)	900-1000	580-1374	e		◆					•		•			
<i>Phytomyza cirsii</i> Hendel, 1923		1150-1200	e									•			
<i>Phytomyza conyzae</i> Hendel, 1920	900-1000		wpo		◆							•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Trachysiphonella ruficeps</i> (Macquart, 1835)	350-500	1150-1600	e	♦								•			
<i>Trachysiphonella scutellata</i> von Roser, 1840	900-1600		eca	♦											
<i>Tricimba</i> (<i>Narishukiella</i>) <i>cincta</i> (Meigen, 1830)	300-1400	800-1150	h	♦							•	•			
<i>Tricimba</i> (<i>Narishukiella</i>) <i>humeralis</i> (Loew, 1858)	300-400		hop	♦											
<i>Cetema</i> (<i>Cetema</i>) <i>cereris</i> (Fallén, 1820)	700-1800	850-1450	hoes	♦			♦					•			
<i>Cetema</i> (<i>Cetema</i>) <i>elongatum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	300-1200	850-1600	h	♦								•			
<i>Cetema</i> (<i>Cetema</i>) <i>myopinum</i> (Loew, 1866)	350-1000	1350-1800	wesca	♦								•			
<i>Cetema</i> (<i>Cetema</i>) <i>neglectum</i> Tonnoir, 1921		1450	e									•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>calceatus</i> Meigen, 1830	350-1200	800-1400	wces	♦							•	•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>fasciatus</i> Meigen, 1830	1900		wces				♦								
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>finitimus</i> Becker, 1910	1230-2350		ewca				♦	♦							
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>geminatus</i> Meigen, 1830	1000-1900	1450	wces				♦					•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>hypostigma</i> Meigen, 1830	900-1000	1150-1200	e				♦					•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>meigenii</i> Loew, 1866	1000-1430		hoes												
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>pumilionis</i> (Bierkander, 1778)		1200-1400	wp, ? wcp									•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>ringens</i> Loew, 1866	1000-1200		wces												
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>scalaris</i> Meigen, 1830	1000-1430		wces												
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>speciosus</i> Meigen, 1830	1140-2500	850-1450	wes				♦	♦				•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Chlorops</i>) <i>trogodytes</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	1000-2000	400-1450	wces				♦					•			
<i>Chlorops</i> (<i>Sclerophallus</i>) <i>limbatus</i> Meigen, 1830	300-1230	360-400	? hoes												
<i>Diplotoxa messoria</i> (Fallén, 1820)		800-1400	h									•			
<i>Elachiptericus italicus</i> Duda, 1933	350	360	se												
<i>Lastosina albipila</i> (Loew, 1866)	350-500		des ?												
<i>Lastosina herpini</i> (Guérin-Ménéville, 1843)	600-1400	400-1374	tp									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>athletica</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	450-1200	1450-1600	csee									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>bohemica</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	350-500	1600	e									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>femorata</i> Macquart, 1835	350-1200	1400-1450	e									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>meigeni</i> Nartshuk, 2006	1600		wes												
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>mosquensis</i> Fedoseeva, 1960		900-1450	e									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>nigriseta</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	1100-1200	850-1150	wces									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>nigriventris</i> Macquart, 1835	350-2200	1150-1600	h									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>pluriseta</i> Péterfi, 1961	1000-1200		wces												
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>pratorem</i> Meigen, 1830		1400-1450	h									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>rohndendorfi</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	1140	850-1150	e									•			
<i>Meromyza</i> (<i>Meromyza</i>) <i>rufa</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	350-1140	900-1600	e									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) saltatrix</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	950-2200	850-1450	h		♦	♦	♦				•	•			
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) triangulina</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	950-1200	850-1150	e		♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) variegata</i> Meigen 1830		1150-1200	e									•			
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) zahvalkini</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	450-1800	1600	des	♦	♦	♦	♦					•	•		
<i>Parectecephala longicornis</i> (Fallén, 1820)	350-500		eswa	♦											
<i>Phyladelphus thalhammeri</i> Becker, 1910	350-500		e, ? cse	♦											
<i>Thaumatomyia elongatula</i> (Becker, 1910)	350-500		e, ? cse	♦											
<i>Thaumatomyia glabra</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1000-1800	360-1450	h	♦	♦	♦	♦			•		•			
<i>Thaumatomyia hallandica</i> Andersson, 1966	350-1450	1400-1450	wces	♦	♦	♦						•	•		
<i>Thaumatomyia notata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	600-2200	850-1450	ppt	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Thaumatomyia rufa</i> (Macquart, 1835)	1500		hop	♦		♦									
<i>Thaumatomyia sulcifrons</i> (Becker, 1907)	600-1000		wcp	♦	♦										
Heleomyzidae															
<i>Orbellia borisregis</i> Czerny, 1930		2005	Er												•
<i>Scoliocentra (Leriola) nigrinervis</i> (Wahlgren, 1918)		2000	wces, ? bm												•
Sphaeroceridae															
<i>Copromyza equina</i> Fallén, 1820		1500	hno												•
<i>Crumomyia rohaceki</i> Norrbom & Kim, 1985		2005	e												•
<i>Pseudocollinella humida</i> (Haliday, 1836)	+++		pat												
<i>Rachispoda lutosa</i> (Stenhammar, 1855)	2020-2392		h				♦	♦							
Camillidae															
<i>Camilla atrimana</i> Strobl, 1910	1000-1200		eswa			♦									
Drosophilidae															
<i>Scaptomyza (Scaptomyza) flava</i> (Fallén, 1823)		1150-1200	h									•			
Diastatidae															
<i>Diastata costata</i> Meigen, 1830	1230	1400	e, ? h			♦						•			
Ephydriidae															
<i>Psilopa nitidula</i> (Fallén, 1813)	300-2575	400-1600	pat	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	•		•			
<i>Psilopa obscuripes</i> Loew, 1860	300-2000		wp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Psilopa polita</i> (Macquart, 1835)	600-2200	400-1600	dp	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦		•		•			
<i>Hydrelia griseola</i> (Fallén, 1813)	600-2500	850-2196	sk	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	•		•	•	•	
<i>Hydrelia maura</i> Meigen, 1838	2200-2500	1500-1600	wp					♦	♦	•		•	•	•	
<i>Dichaeta caudata</i> (Fallén, 1813)		400	h							•					
<i>Notiphila (Notiphila) cinerea</i> Fallén, 1813		1400	tp, ? hop									•			
<i>Notiphila (Notiphila) dorsata</i> Stenhammar, 1844		400	dp, ? wcp							•					

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Notiphila graecula</i> Becker, 1926	1230	1400	ewca			♦						•			
<i>Notiphila nigricornis</i> Stenhammar, 1844	1230	1400	wcp			♦						•			
<i>Notiphila venusta</i> Loew, 1856	1230		dp			♦									
<i>Athyroglossa midiuscula</i> Loew, 1873	350-650		cse, ? cse	♦											
<i>Athyroglossa ordinata</i> Becker, 1896	350-650		wp	♦											
<i>Allotrichoma laterale</i> (Loew, 1860)	350-650		h	♦											
<i>Dicrocerina obscurella</i> (Fallén, 1813)	300-600	400	hnat	♦						•					
<i>Ditrichophora calceata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	700-750		ena	♦											
<i>Ditrichophora fuscella</i> (Stenhammar, 1844)	700-1230		des, ? dp	♦											
<i>Hecamedoides unispinosus</i> (Collin, 1943)	1230		hnat	♦											
<i>Ilythea spilota</i> (Curtis, 1832)	900-1000		h	♦											
<i>Nositima picta</i> (Fallén, 1813)	2000-2190	400-2400	hn				♦			•		•			
<i>Philygria posticata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1000-1200		des	♦											
<i>Philygria stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	600-2100	1400-2400	e	♦			♦					•			
<i>Philygria vittipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	1000-2400		h	♦			♦								
<i>Hyadina guttata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	600-2320	1400	tp	♦			♦								
<i>Parydra (Chaetopnarea) fossarum</i> (Haliday, 1833)	900-1230	2000	h	♦											
<i>Parydra (Parydra) coarctata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	350-700	1500-1600	tp, ? hop	♦								•			
<i>Parydra (Parydra) cognata</i> Loew, 1860	350-700	400-1600	wp	♦						•		•			
<i>Parydra (Parydra) littoralis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	600-2500	400-2000	wp	♦						•		•			
<i>Scatophila caviceps</i> (Stenhammar, 1844)	2500	400	hop	♦			♦		♦	•					
<i>Scatophila despecta</i> (Haliday, 1839)	300-400		h	♦					♦						
<i>Scatophila farinae</i> Becker, 1903	1000-1200		hom	♦											
<i>Linnellia quadrata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	2200-2500	2300	h												•
<i>Lamproscatella bimaculata</i> Hendel, 1933	600-2300	2000	h	♦				♦	♦						•
<i>Lamproscatella sibilans</i> (Haliday, 1833)	1000-2500	2000	h	♦				♦	♦						•
<i>Lamproscatella unipunctata</i> (Becker, 1907)		2000	mca	♦				♦	♦						•
<i>Scatella (Neoscatella) subguttata</i> (Meigen, 1830)		2000	ena, ? sk												•
<i>Scatella (Scatella) paludum</i> (Meigen, 1830)		900-2000	hptn												•
<i>Scatella (Scatella) signalis</i> (Fallén, 1813)	1230	1400-2200	hpta, sk	♦								•			•
<i>Scatella (Scatella) tenuicosta</i> Collin, 1930	600-2500	1400-2200	hat	♦				♦	♦			•			•
CALYPTRATA															
Hippoboscidae															
<i>Hippobosca equina</i> Linnaeus 1758		1350-2100	ppia									•			
<i>Hippobosca longipennis</i> Fabricius 1805		1200-1400	hpt, ? shpt									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Helina depuncta</i> (Fallén, 1825)	900-1200	1500	esca		♦	♦						•			
<i>Helina eyecta</i> (Harris, 1780)	900-1200	400-2000	ppt, ? hpt							•		•			
<i>Helina fraternula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	1810		e		♦	♦									
<i>Helina laxifrons</i> (Zetterstedt, 1860)			h				♦								
<i>Helina latitarsis</i> Ringsdahl, 1924		1200-1400	ean									•			
<i>Helina montana</i> (Rondani, 1866)		1374	dpo, ? wpo									•			
<i>Helina obscurata</i> (Meigen, 1826)		1200-1900	h									•			
<i>Helina pubiseta</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)		1500	e									•			
<i>Helina reverstio</i> (Harris, 1780)		1200-1400	h, ? ho									•			
<i>Mydaea comi</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	1500	1500	hop			♦						•			
<i>Mydaea electra</i> (Zetterstedt, 1860)	300-1000		h	♦	♦										
<i>Mydaea humeralis</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	300-1000		esca	♦	♦										
<i>Myospila mediotubunda</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	1000-1800	400	hno		♦	♦	♦			•					
<i>Hebecnema fumosa</i> (Meigen, 1826)		600-2000	po							•					
<i>Hebecnema umbratica</i> (Meigen, 1826)		1500	ho									•			
<i>Hebecnema vespertina</i> (Fallén, 1823)	300-1500	1150-1500	h		♦	♦						•			
<i>Graphomya maculata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	900-1000	1150-1300	po, ? poa		♦	♦						•			
<i>Spilogona carbonella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)		+++	ean												
<i>Spilogona denigrata</i> (Meigen, 1826)		1500	e									•			
<i>Spilogona dispar</i> (Fallén, 1823)	300-2000	1500-2000	wes		♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Linnophora maculosa</i> (Meigen, 1826)	300-1800		ewca		♦	♦	♦								
<i>Linnophora obsignata</i> (Rondani, 1866)	900-1000		wpat		♦	♦									
Calliphoridae															
<i>Bellardia pandia</i> (Walker 1849)		1600	e									•			
<i>Calliphora genarum</i> (Zetterstedt 1838)		1600	h									•			
<i>Calliphora vicina</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	1810	900	k				♦								
<i>Calliphora vomitoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1810	1200-1400	ha				♦					•			
<i>Lucilia caesar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1810	400-1300	hop				♦			•		•			
<i>Lucilia richardsi</i> Collin, 1926		900-1100	e							•		•			
<i>Lucilia sericata</i> (Meigen, 1826)		550-2100	k							•		•			
<i>Lucilia siharum</i> (Meigen, 1826)		+++	hn												
<i>Protophormia terraenovae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)		1500	h									•			
<i>Pollentia dasyptoda</i> Portschinsky, 1881		900-1100	wpo									•			
<i>Pollentia rudis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		900-1600	hpta									•			
<i>Pollentia tenuiforceps</i> Séguy, 1928		1200-1400	ena									•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Pollenia viatica</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830		1600	ewca									•	•		
<i>Rhyncomya cyanescens</i> (Loew, 1844)		900-1100	hom								•	•			
Sarcophagidae															
<i>Pterella grisea</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1200	wcp									•			
<i>Taxigramma stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)		1100	ena									•			
<i>Metopia argyrocephala</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1100	hno									•			
<i>Metopia campestris</i> (Fallén, 1810)		900-1600	h								•	•	•		
<i>Brachicoma devia</i> (Fallén, 1820)		1200-1800	h								•	•	•		
<i>Eurychaeta muscaria</i> (Meigen, 1826)		1200-1600	ena								•	•	•		
<i>Blaesoxipha (Blaesoxipha) unguilata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)		1600	ena								•	•	•		
<i>Blaesoxipha (Servatisia) erythrura</i> (Meigen 1826)	900-1000		eca		♦	♦									
<i>Blaesoxipha (Servatisia) rossica</i> Villeneuve, 191	1810-2000	900-1200	esca				♦				•	•			
<i>Ravinia pernix</i> (Harris, 1780)	900-1000	900-1200	po				♦				•	•			
<i>Sarcophaga (Bellieriomima) subulata</i> Pandellé, 1896			wes		♦	♦									
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) agnata</i> Rondani, 1860		1150	e									•			
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) crassimargo</i> Pandellé, 1896	2000		wesca				♦								
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) maculata</i> Meigen, 1835	1810		sp, ? wcp				♦								
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) noveboracensis</i> Rondani, 1860		1150-1600	e									•	•		
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) noveboracensis</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	2000		ena				♦					•			
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) rosellei</i> Böttcher, 1912		1150	des									•			
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) nigriventris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	2400		dp					♦							
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) socrus</i> Rondani, 1860	1810		e				♦								
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) soror</i> Rondani, 1860	1950-2200		e				♦								
<i>Sarcophaga (Sarcotachinella) sinuata</i> Meigen, 1826	1810		h				♦								
<i>Sarcophaga (Krameromyia) anaces</i> Walker, 1849		630-700	h												
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) benaci</i> Böttcher, 1913		1600	cse							•		•	•		
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) dissimilis</i> Meigen, 1826		400-1600	des							•		•	•		
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) infantilis</i> Böttcher, 1913	1950-2200	630-700	e				♦	♦		•					
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) mutilla</i> Villeneuve, 1912	1950-2400		csee				♦	♦							
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) porrecta</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	1950-2200	1200-2200	se, m				♦	♦				•	•	•	
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) schineri</i> Bezzi, 1891		1150-1600	e									•	•	•	
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) vagans</i> Meigen, 1826		1150-1600	hoes				♦	♦				•	•	•	
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) vicina</i> Macquart, 1835	1950-2400		e												
<i>Sarcophaga (Bercaea) africa</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	300-400	400	sk		♦					•					
<i>Sarcophaga (Liosarcophaga) jacobsoni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)		400	tp							•					

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Oswaldia muscaria</i> (Fallén, 1810)	1250		des			♦									
<i>Oswaldia spectabilis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	850-1250	850-1150	e		♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Lomachantha parva</i> Rondani, 1859	1100-1400		et			♦									
<i>Eryniopsis antennata</i> (Rondani, 1861)	300-450	360-545	? hom, h*	♦		♦				•					
<i>Blondelia nigripes</i> (Fallén, 1810)	300-2400	360-2360	tp, h*	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦		•	•	•	•	•	
<i>Compsitura concinnata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-1300	500-1400	hocs, h*	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Vibrissina turrita</i> (Meigen, 1824)	1000-1400		dp		♦	♦									
<i>Acemya acuticornis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	900-1200		ess		♦	♦									
<i>Smidtia amoena</i> (Meigen, 1824)	450-1230	500-900	hocs	♦	♦	♦				•					
<i>Winthemia quadripustulata</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	350-1300	1150-1400	h	♦	♦	♦					•				
<i>Nemorilla floralis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	300-650		hop	♦											
<i>Aplomya confinis</i> (Fallén, 1820)	500-1350	400-1650	hop	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•	•		
<i>Phebellia nigripalpis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1847)	400-1400		des	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Tlephusa cinctina</i> (Rondani, 1859)	700-900		ess		♦										
<i>Epicampocera succincta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	700-1500	1200-1500	tp		♦	♦					•				
<i>Phryxe nemea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	400-1950	800-1900	hocs	♦	♦	♦	♦			•	•	•	•		
<i>Phryxe prima</i> (Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1889)	700-750		mt		♦										
<i>Phryxe vulgaris</i> (Fallén, 1810)	350-2000	1000-2000	h	♦	♦	♦	♦			•	•	•	•		
<i>Periarcticlops scutellaris</i> (Fallén, 1820)		500-1100	wces							•	•	•			
<i>Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata</i> (Walker, 1853)	700-1450	1500	des		♦	♦									
<i>Lydella stabulans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	500-700		wes	♦											
<i>Cadurciella tritaeniata</i> (Rondani, 1859)	450-700		des	♦											
<i>Drino atropivora</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	300-1300	900-1300	sp	♦	♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Drino inconspicua</i> (Meigen, 1830)	1200-1300	1000-1300	wces		♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Drino lota</i> (Meigen, 1824)	700-1300		pat		♦	♦									
<i>Drino vicina</i> (Zetterstedt, 1849)	500-1300	900	wces	♦	♦	♦					•				
<i>Huebneria affinis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	450-2400	900-2000	ess	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦		•	•	•	•		
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) bombylans</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	1750-1800		des				♦								
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) gnava</i> (Meigen, 1824)	700-1000	690-1000	des		♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) luconum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	600-1300	1400	tp	♦	♦	♦						•			
<i>Erycia festinans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	800-1300		wces	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Alsomyia capillata</i> (Rondani, 1859)	500-1000		hom	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Platymya fimbriata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	2000-2500	2200-2370	tp, bm	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦					•	
<i>Eumeca linearicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	700-1300	600-1350	hocs		♦	♦				•	•	•	•		
<i>Eumeca mitis</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1300	hocs									•	•		

Table 2. Continued

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Zenillia libatrix</i> (Panzer, 1798)			1300-1600	hoses												
<i>Clemelis pullata</i> (Meigen, 1824)		500-2400	900-2350	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦							
<i>Pates pavida</i> (Meigen, 1824)		400-1300	400-1350	hop	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Pates pumicata</i> (Meigen, 1824)		350-700	1300-1600	nm	♦											
<i>Phryno vetula</i> (Meigen, 1824)		500-700		des	♦											
<i>Bothria frontosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)		900-1300		hoses		♦	♦									
<i>Ceromasia rubrifrons</i> (Macquart, 1834)			800-1400	hoses												
<i>Allophorocera ferruginea</i> (Meigen, 1824)		700-1950	900-1950	hoses	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Allophorocera pachystyla</i> (Macquart, 1850)		2000	1800-2000	e, m												
<i>Eurysthaea scutellaris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1848)		350-700	350-800	e	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Elodia ambulatoria</i> (Meigen, 1824)		700-1300		wcp		♦	♦									
<i>Surmia bella</i> (Meigen, 1824)		400-1400	900-1400	po	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Blepharipa pratensis</i> (Meigen, 1824)		350-1400	500-1400	tp, h*	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Masceera pavoniae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)		400-1000	400-1000	wp	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Masceera silvatica</i> (Fallén, 1810)		350-1250	900-1000	e	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Prosopaea nigricans</i> (Egger, 1861)		350-1300	800-1100	wcp	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Gaedia connexa</i> (Meigen, 1824)		700-1400		e	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Gaedia distincta</i> Egger, 1861		900-1350		ess	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Baumhaueria goniaeformis</i> (Meigen, 1824)		900-1350		wp	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Gonia bimaculata</i> Wiedemann, 1819		350-900	400-1000	atm	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Gonia capitata</i> (De Geer, 1776)		700-2000	500-1900	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Gonia ornata</i> Meigen, 1826		300-450		wcp	♦											
<i>Gonia picea</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)		350-650		wcp	♦											
<i>Pseudogonia parisiaca</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851)		300-1300		ess	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Pseudogonia rufifrons</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)		350-700		ppta	♦											
<i>Spallanzania hebes</i> (Fallén, 1820)		300-700	400-600	ho	♦											
<i>Tachina (Tachina) grossa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		350-1400	350-1300	hoses	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Tachina (Tachina) magna</i> (Giglio-Tos, 1890)		300-650		sess	♦											
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) casta</i> (Rondani, 1859)		350-600	500-550	nm	♦											
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) fera</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)		300-1900	340-1900	hop	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) magnicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)		300-1900	350-1900	hop	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) nupta</i> (Rondani, 1859)		300-1750	300-1750	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Tachina (Servillia) lurida</i> (Fabricius, 1781)		300-600	350-660	wp	♦											
<i>Tachina (Echinogaster) praeceps</i> Meigen, 1824		350-1300	350-1300	wp	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Nowickia (Nowickia) marklini</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)		1250-2300	1200-2300	h, ? bm	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦							

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Macquartia chalconota</i> (Meigen, 1824)	500-1300	900-1300	wes	♦	♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Macquartia dispar</i> (Fallén, 1820)	500-1400	600-1400	ess	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Macquartia grisea</i> (Fallén, 1810)	500-800	600-700	e	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Macquartia praefica</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-1250	600-1250	hom	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Macquartia tenebricosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-1800	400-1600	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦			•	•	•			
<i>Macquartia tessellum</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1300-1400	mca								•	•			
<i>Phytomyptera abnormis</i> (Stein, 1924)	300-400	1000-1500	se	♦							•	•			
<i>Phytomyptera cingulata</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)			e												
<i>Graphogaster brunnescens</i> Villeneuve, 1907		400	ess							•					
<i>Actia crassicornis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	800-1500	600-1500	ess		♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Actia infantula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)		400-1000	wcp							•	•				
<i>Actia pilipennis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	300-700		hoes	♦	♦										
<i>Peribaea tibialis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851)	300-1000	550-1000	spat	♦	♦					•	•				
<i>Siphona cristata</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	350-1000	480-1150	h	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Siphona flavifrons</i> Staeger, 1849	1700-1900		des, h*				♦								
<i>Siphona geniculata</i> (De Geer, 1776)	800-1300		hoes, h*		♦	♦									
<i>Aphria latifrons</i> Villeneuve, 1908		900	mss								•				
<i>Aphria longirostris</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-2300	600-2000	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦		•	•	•	•		
<i>Demoticius plebejus</i> (Fallén, 1810)	1000-1950	900-1100	wes				♦			•	•	•			
<i>Bithia glirina</i> (Rondani, 1861)	350-1450	360-1450	wes	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Bithia modesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-1200	460-1200	hom	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Leskia aurea</i> (Fallén, 1820)	700-900	700-900	hoes	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Mimtho rufiventris</i> (Fallén, 1817)	350-1000	350-900	tp	♦	♦					•	•				
<i>Microphthalma europaea</i> Egger, 1860	700-900	500-600	? om	♦	♦					•					
<i>Dexiosoma caninum</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	1100-1300		des				♦								
<i>Trixa caerulea</i> Meigen, 1824		400	wes							•					
<i>Trixa conspersa</i> (Harris, 1776)		400	wes							•					
<i>Billaea fortis</i> (Rondani, 1862)	650-800	650-800	des		♦					•	•				
<i>Billaea irrorata</i> (Meigen, 1826)		350-550	e							•					
<i>Billaea pectinata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	350-1250	400-1200	mca	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Billaea triangulifera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	1100-1700	1000-1200	hoes			♦	♦			•	•	•			
<i>Dinera carinifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	300-2400	400-2550	hoes	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦		•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Dinera ferina</i> (Fallén, 1817)	500-1600	500-1600	wes	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Dinera grisea</i> (Fallén, 1817)		400-500	esca							•					

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Estheria bohemani</i> (Rondani, 1862)	1000-1800		e			♦	♦					•			
<i>Estheria cristata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	400-1900	1374	e	♦								•			
<i>Estheria petiolata</i> (Bonsdorff, 1866)	300-1800	1000-1600	wces	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Estheria picta</i> (Meigen, 1826)	300-1800	400-1600	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Dexia rustica</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	350-1000	600-1100	hocs	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Prosenia siberita</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	500-1800	500-1600	hpta	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Zeuxia brevicornis</i> (Egger, 1860)		400	nmca												
<i>Zeuxia cinerea</i> Meigen, 1826	500-1900	500-2000	wp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•		•	
<i>Zeuxia erythraea</i> (Egger, 1856)		400	nm												
<i>Eriothrix apenninus</i> (Rondani, 1862)	900-2450	1350-2350	wp		♦	♦	♦	♦	♦			•		•	
<i>Eriothrix rufomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1776)	350-2450	1150-2300	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦	♦			•		•	
<i>Ramonda spathulata</i> (Fallén, 1820)	400-1350	1350-1475	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Pentsepsia carbonaria</i> (Panzer, 1798)	350-700	600-700	ppt	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Athyrcia impressa</i> (Wulp, 1869)	1300		ess			♦									
<i>Athyrcia trepida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-1200	400-1200	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Voria ruralis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	700-1800	400-1800	k		♦	♦	♦					•		•	
<i>Hyleorus elatus</i> (Meigen, 1838)	350-1300		hocs	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Phyllomya volvulus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	450-1750	1150-1200	hocs	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Thelaira nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	350-1300	400-670	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Halidayia aurea</i> Egger, 1856	350-900	900-1000	hocs	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Stomina calidrata</i> (Rondani, 1862)	350-1000	670-1100	mca	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Stomina iners</i> (Meigen, 1838)		900-1000	hom									•			
<i>Stomina tachinoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)	350-950	400	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Rhamphina pedemontana</i> (Meigen, 1824)	1800	800-1300	se, ? nm				♦					•			
<i>Dufouria chalybeata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-1300		dp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Dufouria nigrita</i> (Fallén, 1810)	500-950	400-900	wcp	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Chetoptilia puella</i> (Rondani, 1862)	600-900		des	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Eliozeta helluo</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	300-700	400-800	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Eliozeta pellucens</i> (Fallén, 1820)	300-1000	400-900	des	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Clytiomya contima</i> (Panzer, 1798)	350-1300	360-1000	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Ectophasia crassipennis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	300-1700	350-1200	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Ectophasia leucoptera</i> (Rondani, 1865)	300-450		nmt	♦											
<i>Ectophasia oblonga</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	300-1200	300-1150	wp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Gymnosoma clavatum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1947)	350-1700	500-1500	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Gymnosoma costatum</i> (Panzer, 1800)	350-1000	800-1000	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			
<i>Gymnosoma desertorum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1947)	350-1250		ceca	♦	♦	♦	♦								
<i>Gymnosoma dolycoridis</i> Dupuis, 1961	350-1250	500-1200	ess	♦	♦	♦	♦					•			

Table 2. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
<i>Gymnosoma inornatum</i> Zimin, 1966	350-1250	380-1150	tp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Gymnosoma nitens</i> Meigen, 1824	650-1400	1000	esca	♦	♦	♦					•	•			
<i>Gymnosoma nudifrons</i> Hering, 1966	650-1300		hoes	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Gymnosoma rotundatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	350-1800	350-1600	tp	♦	♦	♦	♦			•	•	•			
<i>Cistogaster globosa</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	300-450		ess	♦	♦										
<i>Opesia cana</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-900		ess	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Elomya lateralis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-1400	350-1400	tp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Phasia (Phasia) aurulans</i> Meigen, 1824		400	hoes	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Phasia (Phasia) hemiptera</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		400	hoes	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Phasia (Phasia) obesa</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	750-1550	750-1500	tp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Phasia (Phasia) subcoleoprata</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	700-1300	400-1200	tp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Phasia (Hyalomya) pusilla</i> Meigen, 1824	350-1000	350-1100	tp	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Strongygaster globula</i> (Meigen, 1824)	500-950		hoes	♦	♦										
<i>Dionaea aurifrons</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-1250	450-600	tp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Leucostoma anthracinum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-550		wces	♦	♦										
<i>Leucostoma tetraptera</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-1250	400-1300	wcp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Clairvillia biguttata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	350-950	500-700	dp	♦	♦					•	•	•			
<i>Labigastera forcipata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	700-1300	900-1300	wes	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Labigastera pauciseta</i> (Rondani, 1861)	350-1250		e, cse	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) bicolor</i> (Olivier, 1812)	300-1400	400-1300	mca	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brassicaria</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	350-1800	350-1700	hop	♦	♦	♦	♦			•	•	•	•		
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brevicornis</i> (Loew, 1844)	380-1300	450-1200	des	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) pilipes</i> (Loew, 1844)	500-900	480-900	wcp	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Ocypterula) pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)		1200-1300	mss	♦	♦							•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Dupuisia) crassa</i> (Loew, 1845)	350-950	900	mss	♦	♦						•	•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Caloclyptera) intermedia</i> (Meigen, 1824)	450-1250	400-1300	h	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			
<i>Cylindromyia (Neoclyptera) auriceps</i> (Meigen, 1838)	350-1000		tp	♦	♦										
<i>Cylindromyia (Neoclyptera) interrupta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	500-1250		h	♦	♦	♦									
<i>Hemysda vittata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	600-700		hoes	♦	♦										
<i>Besseria anthophila</i> (Loew, 1871)		1300	wcp	♦	♦							•			
<i>Besseria dimidiata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	700-800		e	♦	♦										
<i>Besseria lateritia</i> (Meigen, 1824)	300-600		? mt	♦	♦										
<i>Phania funesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	450-950	450-1000	e	♦	♦	♦				•	•	•			

* - Species of Limoniidae and Peditidae that are not included in the work concerning Pirin Mts. from 2015 (HUBENOV, 2015b)

Table 3. Similarity of the Diptera fauna by vegetation belts in percentages

Vegetation belts of the Pirin Mts.	Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	40.8 (108)					
2		46.6 (163)				
3			40.9 (234)			
4				30.7 (83)		
5					25.7 (23)	
6						0 (0)

Note. 1 – Xerothermic oak forests, 2 – Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic oak-hornbeam forests, 3 – Beech forests, 4 – Coniferous forests, 5 – Subalpine vegetation, 6 – Alpine vegetation; Common species are given in brackets.

ferences between the Pirin and Rila Mountains (from 11.3% to 18.3%) in the number of species in the first three vegetation belts (especially the beech belt). They are probably owing to the specific climatic conditions of the two mountains, the nature of the plant communities in the karst areas of the Pirin Mts. and the insufficient research of most families. The altitude of the localities, from which the most material was collected, is also important.

The upper limit of the coniferous zone passes into the subalpine vegetation zones with a mixture of regions at about 200 m a.s.l. Thus, most of the species were common for both vegetation belts and the number of taxa established in the subalpine belt of the two mountains increased (79 species or 10.6% in the Pirin Mts. and 99 species or 9.8% in the Rila Mts.). Among the species found in the alpine belt (29 species or 3.9% in the Pirin Mts. and 26 species or 2.6% in the Rila Mts.), only four taxa collected from the Rila Mts. were typical for this belt (*Molophilus lautereri* Stary – Bulgarian endemic of Limoniidae, *Micropsectra radialis* Goet. – Palearctic-Oriental species of Chironomidae, *Eudorylas jenkinsoni* Coe – European species of Pipunculidae, and *Didea alneti* Fall. – Holarctic species of Syrphidae). All other species were established in the subalpine belt and most of them in other vegetation belts as well. In some cases, the finding of species at certain altitude takes place accidentally. The lack of systematic research on Diptera of the Pirin and Rila Mts., and the fragmentary data for most families do not allow explicit conclusions about the adherence of taxa to one or another vegetation zone to be made. The distribution of species in groups according to their presence in the vegetation belts had a relative character and depended on the specific features of taxa and research area,

as well as on the duration of the research. There was a correlation between the horizontal and vertical distribution of Diptera. Species found in the subalpine and alpine zones (above 2200 m a.s.l.) have large areals (12 Superpalaeartic, nine Palearctic, ten Eurosiberian and three Mediterranean species). In these two belts of the Pirin and Rila Mts. Holarctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalaeartic, West and Central Palearctic, West Palearctic, European-North African, Holoeurosiberian, West and Central Eurosiberian, West Eurosiberian, Disjunct Eurosiberian and European species prevailed (Table 4). The differences of the taxa distribution in the subalpine and alpine zones were small: from 0.7 to 1.3% for both mountains. The differences between the separate areographical categories were higher and reached up to 5.4–7.5% (for the Holarctic species).

The zoogeographical categorisation of the species (Table 2) was made on the basis of current data about their distribution. Thus, the dipterans were divided into 92 areographical categories, combined into two main groups and six subgroups (Table 4).

Species distributed in the Palearctic and beyond it. This group (156 species or 21.0% in the Pirin Mts. and 258 species or 25.7% in the Rila Mts.) included 29 categories, of which 24 combined species of northern type (widely distributed in the Holarctic and Palearctic), and five – species of southern type (distributed only in the southern parts of the Palearctic). The difference between the separate vegetation belts with respect to this group in the two mountains was from 0.4 to 23.9% (from 13 to 87 species) for the Pirin Mts., and from 0.4 to 16.1% (from 11 to 196 species) for the Rila Mts. There was a more significant difference of 10% between the mountains in the first vegetation belt. In the oth-

er vegetation belts this difference was small (0.2-5.3%). The establishment of other species of the group of the northern type in the last two vegetation belts is very likely, owing to their distribution and insufficient studies of the higher parts of the mountain. It is accepted that the species of the northern type have vast areas and ecological flexibility. In the Superpalaeartic complex the Holarctic species (72 species or 9.7% in the Pirin Mts. and 124 species or 12.4% in the Rila Mts.) prevailed as compared to the other areographical categories where the Holarctic-Oriental (23-31 species or 3.1%) and Palaeartic-Oriental (13-29 species or 1.7-2.9%) forms were present. The species of the southern type were represented in the first three vegetation belts (1-3 in the Pirin Mts. and 1-2 in the Rila Mts.). The group was not important for the zoogeographical characteristic of the dipterans in the studied region because of the small number of species (three – five species or 0.3-0.5%). Usually the species of the whole group, distributed in the Palaeartic and beyond it, were scantily presented and they were not determinant for the zoogeographical characteristic of taxa in the Bulgarian terrestrial fauna. Only in a highly mobile forms (such as Diptera), the group was well presented and could reach 20-25%. It was better represented in the Rila Mts. than in the Pirin Mts. In the two-winged insects significant numbers of synanthropic and synoviol forms with cosmopolitan or subcosmopolitan distribution occurred. They had anthropogenic areas, structured with the development of human civilisation (before the contemporary studies).

Species distributed only in the Palaeartic but in more than one subregion (Palaeartic type). Taxa, whose areas include more than one Palaeartic subregion in latitudinal direction, belong to this group. They were well represented in the high mobile groups and comprised about 25-35% of the species composition. Nineteen areographical categories were registered from both mountains (Table 4). A total of 204 species (27.5%) from the Pirin Mts. and 259 species (25.8%) from the Rila Mts. of this group have been established. Their character was determined by the Transpalaeartic (57 species or 7.8% from the Pirin Mts. and 78 species or 7.8% from the Rila Mts.), West Palaeartic (26 species or 3.5% from the Pirin Mts. and 46 species or 4.6% from the Rila Mts.) and European-North African (26 species or 3.5% from the Pirin Mts.

and 35 species or 3.5% from the Rila Mts.) species. The correlation of these categories remained the same in the separate vegetation belts and ranged from 0.2 to 11.0% (from six to 117 species) in the Pirin Mts. and from 1.6% to 12.2% (from three to 196 species) in the Rila Mts. The Holopalaeartic, West and Central Palaeartic and Eurosiberian-Central Asian species (eight-24 species or 1.1-3.2% from the Pirin Mts. and 18-23 species or 1.8-2.3% from the Rila Mts.) were well presented. Thirteen species from the Pirin Mts. and eight species from the Rila Mts. had a longitudinal disjunction of the areas with regard to Siberia and Central Asia. Probably some of these species were represented with sparse populations and could be found as a result of further studies. Most often, a latitudinal disjunction of the areas of this group lacks (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988; HUBENOV, 2015a). Rarely single boreomontane forms are presented. A significant part of the species with wide vertical distribution (more than 25%) belonged to this group. It included from 20.7% to 37.0% (from six to 117 species) of the species composition of the separate vegetation belts of the Pirin Mts. and from 11.5% to 31.2% (from three to 196 species) of the species of the different vegetation belts of the Rila Mts. (Table 3). The vast areas and wide vertical distribution of the taxa of this group are an indication of the greater ecological flexibility of its species. This group was represented a little better in terms of relative abundance in the Pirin Mts. (with 1.7% more).

Species distributed within one subregion of the Palaeartic. This group (382 species or 51.5% from the Pirin Mts. and 486 species or 48.5% from the Rila Mts.) included species with Eurosiberian and Mediterranean type of distribution (36 areographical categories). Endemics were included in this group as well. The Mediterranean-Central Asian species are also included here according to KRYZHANOVSKY (1965) and LOPATIN (1989) who combine the Mediterranean and Central Asian subregions. The species with Mediterranean type of distribution are accepted in a general way and include faunistic elements (Submediterranean, Subiranian and Pontian) that could be considered separately as well (GRUEV & KUSMANOV, 1994, 1999; GRUEV, 1995, GRUEV & BECHEV, 2000).

The **Eurosiberian species** (combined into 13 areographical categories) were 328 (44.2%)

Table 4. Zoogeographical characteristic of Diptera (Insecta) from the vegetation belts of the studied mountains
Note. The percentage of main categories and these with more species is presented

Areographical categories	Total numbers, % - Pirin Mts.	Total numbers, % - Rila Mts.	Vegetation belts of the Pirin Mts.						Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.					
			4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Species distributed in Palearctic and out of it	156 21.0	258 25.7	57 20.9	78 22.3	87 21.3	71 26.8	28 35.4	13 44.8	79 30.9	92 26.2	196 26.6	74 26.7	31 31.3	11 42.3
NORTH TYPE	151 20.3	255 25.4	53 19.4	74 21.2	86 21.0	71 26.8	28 35.4	13 44.8	76 29.7	90 25.6	196 26.6	74 26.7	31 31.3	11 42.3
Cosmopolitan (k)	6	7	3	4	5	6	2	1	6	7	6	5		
Semiosmopolitan (sk)	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical (hptn)	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2		
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian (hpta)	3	5	2	2	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	2		
Holarctic-Paleotropical (hpt)	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental (hno)	5	9		2	2	4	2		4	3	6	1	2	1
Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical (hnat)	2	2	1		1				2	1	1	1		
Holarctic-Oriental-Australian (hoa)		1									1			
Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian (hata)		1									1			
Holarctic-Neotropical (hn)	3	4	1	1	1	3	1		2	3	2	2	2	1
Holarctic-Afrotropical (hat)	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	
Holarctic-Oriental (ho)	23 3.1	31 3.1	7 2.6	12 3.4	13 3.2	8 3.0	2 2.5	1 3.4	10 3.9	12 3.4	23 3.1	9 3.2	1 1.0	1 3.8
Holarctic-Australian (ha)	2	5		1		1			1	2	3			
Palearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (ppta)	4	3	3	2	1		1		1	2	3	1		
Palearctic-Afrotropical-Australian (pata)		1									1			
Palearctic-Oriental-Australian (poa)		2							1	1	2			
Palearctic-Paleotropical (ppt)	4	6	3	3	2	2	1		3	3	5	1		

Table 4. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Palaeartic-Afrotropical (pat)	3	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1		
Palaeartic-Oriental (po)	13	29	5	8	9	5	2	2	11	12	26	9	3	2
	1.7	2.9	1.8	2.3	2.2	1.9	2.5	6.9	4.3	3.4	3.5	3.2	3.0	7.7
Palaeartic-Australian (pa)	1	1				1	1					1	1	1
West Palaeartic-Oriental (wpo)	2	10		2					1	2	7	1		
Disjunct Palaeartic-Oriental (dpo)	1	1			1						1			
West Palaeartic-Afrotropical (wpat)	1				1									
Holarctic (h)	72	124	22	29	40	34	10	4	25	31	94	34	20	5
	9.7	12.4	8.1	8.3	9.8	12.8	12.7	13.8	9.8	8.8	12.8	12.3	20.2	19.2
SOUTH TYPE	5	3	4	4	1				3	2				
	0.7	0.3	1.5	1.1	0.2				1.2	0.6				
South Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian (sppta)	1			1	1									
South Palaeartic-Afrotropical (spat)	1	1	1	1					1	1				
Paleotropical-Mediterranean (ptm)	1		1											
Afrotropical-Mediterranean (atm)	1	1	1	1					1	1				
Oriental-Mediterranean (om)	1	1	1	1					1					
Species with Palaeartic distribution	586	745	216	271	322	194	51	16	177	259	540	203	68	15
	79.0	74.3	79.1	77.6	78.7	73.2	64.5	55.2	69.1	73.8	73.4	73.3	68.7	57.7
PALAEARTIC TYPE	204	259	101	112	117	65	19	6	80	103	196	75	24	3
	27.5	25.8	37.0	32.1	28.6	24.5	24.0	20.7	31.2	29.3	26.6	27.1	24.2	11.5
Holopalaearctic (hop)	19	18	15	14	14	7	2	2	10	13	17	7		
	2.5	1.8	5.5	4.0	3.4	2.6	2.5	6.9	3.9	3.7	2.3	2.5		
Transpalaeartic (tp)	58	78	33	38	37	23	5	2	30	43	61	21	8	1
	7.8	7.8	12.1	10.9	9.0	8.7	6.3	6.9	11.7	12.2	8.3	7.6	8.1	3.8
West and Central Palaeartic (wcp)	24	23	15	15	15	8	2		11	11	18	6	2	1
	3.2	2.3	5.5	4.3	3.7	3.0	2.5		4.3	3.1	2.4	2.2	2.0	3.8
West Palaeartic (wp)	26	46	17	14	15	10	6	2	14	14	35	16	6	
	3.5	4.6	6.2	4.0	3.7	3.8	7.8	6.9	5.5	4.0	4.7	5.8	6.1	
Disjunct Palaeartic (dp)	13	8	6	5	6	2	3		4	2	4	1	1	1
South Palaeartic (sp)	2	3	1	1	1	1				1	3			
European-Anatolian-North African (eanna)		1												
European-North African (ena)	26	35	3	11	9	6			4	8	27	12	3	
	3.5	3.5	1.1	3.2	2.2	2.3			1.6	2.3	3.7	4.3	3.0	
Euro Siberian-Anatolian-Central Asian (esanca)		1									1			
Euro Siberian-Central Asian (esca)	8	22	5	4	3				3	5	13	5	1	
	1.1	2.2	1.8	1.1	0.7				1.2	1.4	1.8	1.8	0.1	

Table 4. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
West Eurosiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian (wesanca)	1								1					
West Eurosiberian-Central Asian (wesca)	2	1	1	1	1	1					1	1		
West Eurosiberian-Iran-Turanian (wesit)	1											1	1	
European-Central Asian (eca)	3	2		3	3						1			
East European-Central Asian (eeca)	1		1	1	1									
European-West Central Asian (ewca)	5	4	1	2	3	3	1		1	1	4	1		
European-South-west Asian (eswa)	6	4	3	1	2	2			1	1	2	3	1	
European-Iran-Turanian (eit)	8	8		1	5	2				3	7	1	1	
European-Turanian (et)	3	3		1	3				1	1	2			
EUROSIBERIAN TYPE	328 44.2	429 42.8	86 31.5	139 39.8	187 45.7	117 44.1	28 35.4	9 31.0	78 30.5	139 39.6	315 42.8	119 43.0	40 40.4	11 42.3
Holoeuro Siberian (hoes)	50	82	21	33	34	23	3	1	16	27	60	24	6	2
	6.7	8.2	7.7	9.5	8.3	8.7	3.8	3.4	6.2	7.7	8.1	8.7	6.1	7.7
West and Central Euro Siberian (wces)	29	27	9	9	22	10	2	1	5	10	21	7	1	1
	3.9	2.7	3.3	2.6	5.4	3.8	2.5	3.4	1.9	2.8	2.8	2.5	1.0	3.8
West Eurosiberian (wes)	27	42	9	11	15	11	2	1	8	14	31	8	2	
	3.6	4.2	3.3	3.2	3.7	4.1	2.5	3.4	3.1	4.0	4.2	2.9	2.0	
Disjunct Eurosiberian (des)	39	34	11	15	22	12	4	2	7	14	22	11	1	
	5.2	3.4	4.0	4.3	5.4	4.5	5.1	6.9	2.7	4.0	3.0	3.0	1.0	
European and South Siberian (ess)	11	6	5	9	8	1	1		4	4	5	1		
European-Anatolian (ean)	4	10	1	3	2	1			1	2	5	3	2	
European (e)	141	183	27	50	70	48	12	4	32	60	138	47	18	4
	19.0	18.2	9.9	14.3	17.1	18.1	15.2	13.8	12.5	17.1	18.7	17.0	18.2	15.4
Central and East European (cee)		2									2			
Central and South European-Anatolian (csean)	3	5		1	3	1				1	5	4	2	2
Central and South-east European-Anatolian (csean)		2							1	1	1	1	1	
Central and South-east European-Lebanonian (cseel)		1									1	1	1	1
Central and South European (cse)	18	25	2	5	8	7	3		2	4	18	9	4	1
	2.4	2.5	0.7	1.4	2.0	2.6	3.8		0.8	1.1	2.4	3.2	4.0	3.8
Central and South-east European (csee)	6	10	1	3	3	3	1		2	2	6	3	2	
MEDITERRANEAN TYPE	41 5.5	45 4.5	28 10.3	19 5.4	11 2.7	6 2.3	3 3.8	1 3.4	19 7.4	17 4.8	23 3.1	6 2.2	2 2.0	
Mediterranean and South Siberian (mss)	1	3	1	1						2	1			

Table 4. Continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Mediterranean and South-west Siberian (mws)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Mediterranean-Central Asian (mca)	6	6	5	4	3	1	1	1	4	3	3	1		
North Mediterranean-Central Asian (nmca)	0.8	0.6	1.8	1.1	0.7	0.4	1.3	3.4	1.6	0.8	0.3	0.4		
Mediterranean-West Central Asian (mwca)	2	2	1	2	1				1		1			
Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian (nemit)	1		1						1					
Mediterranean-Turanian (mt)	2	1	1	1										
North Mediterranean-Turanian (nmt)	3	1	1	2					1	1	1			
South European and South Siberian (sess)	2	1	1	1	1	1			1	1	1	1		
Central and South European-Iran-Turanian (cseit)	1	2	1								1			
Central and South-east European-Iran-Turanian (cseit)	1				1									
Central and South European-North African (csena)	1	1		1	1					1	1	1		
South European-North African (sena)		1									1			
Holomediterranean (hom)	10	8	9	3	2	2	1		4	5	3			
North Mediterranean (nm)	1.3	0.8	3.3	0.9	0.5	0.8	1.3		1.6	1.4	0.3			
South European (se)	4	6	4	2	2				4	1	2			
South-east European (see)	0.5	0.6	1.5	0.6	0.5				1.6	0.3	0.3			
East Mediterranean (em)	3	7	1			2	1		2	1	5	2	1	
Balkan-Anatolian (ban)	0.4	0.7	0.4			0.8	1.3		0.8	0.3	0.7	0.7	1.0	
ENDEMICS	1	1		1							1	1	1	
Balkan subendemic (Ebs)	2	3	2	1					1	2	2			
Balkan endemic (Eb)	13	12	1	1	7	6	1		1	2	6	3	2	1
Bulgarian endemic (Ebg)	1.7	1.2	0.4	0.3	1.7	2.3	1.3				0.8	1.1	2.0	3.8
Regional endemic (Er)	1	2				1						1	1	
	4	1	1	1	3	4					1			
	6	7			3	4					5	1		1
	0.8	0.7			0.7	1.5					0.7	0.4		3.8
	2	2			1	1	1					1	1	
Total 1351 species	759	1003	273	349	409	265	79	29	256	351	736	277	99	26
	56.2	74.2	36.8	47.0	55.1	35.7	10.6	3.9	25.5	35.0	73.4	27.6	9.9	2.6

from the Pirin Mts. and 429 (42.8%) from the Rila Mts. The European species were most numerous (141 species or 19.0% from the Pirin Mts. and 183 species or 18.2% from the Rila Mts.), followed by the Holoeurosiberian (50 species or 6.7% from the Pirin Mts. and 82 species or 8.2% from the Rila Mts.) and the Disjunct Eurosiberian (39 species or 5.2% from the Pirin Mts. and 34 species or 3.4% from the Rila Mts.) species. The ratio of these categories was different for the specific families (the Holoeurosiberian, Disjunct Eurosiberian and European species of the family Tachinidae were almost equal in number as the Eurosiberian forms were 50% in total, while in other families the Central and South European species were better represented). The number of taxa from the mentioned categories in the separate vegetation belts ranged from 1.0% to 18.7% (one – 138 species) and increased (as a percentage) with height up to 2200 m a.s.l. The West and Central Eurosiberian, West Eurosiberian and Central and South European species were well represented. Most Eurosiberian species were found in the beech and coniferous forest belts (42.8-45.7%). In the subalpine and alpine zones of the Rila Mts., the Eurosiberian species predominated over the other zoogeographical categories (40.4-42.3%), whereas in the Pirin Mts. they were poorly represented (31.0-35.4%). The differences in the Eurosiberian species (as a percentage) in the other vegetation belts of the Pirin and Rila Mts. were smaller (2.9% for the beech belt). A number of disjunctive areas were represented: longitudinal disjunction for Siberia and Central Asia (Table 2, 4) and latitudinal disjunction with the typical for the Eurosiberian complex boreomontane, boreoalpine and arctic-alpine distribution (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988; HUBENOV, 2015a). Interesting is the significant presence of Eurosiberian species in the first two vegetation belts of the Pirin and Rila Mountains, which can be explained in two ways: 1) It is possible that a part of these species have unclear Palaearctic distribution; 2) It is supposed that the humid mountain valleys characterised with cooler climate have facilitated the migration of the above-mentioned forms to the lowlands. Finding Eurosiberian boreomontane forms at low altitudes has also been reported for other insect groups as Heteroptera, Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) and Tachinidae (Diptera) (JOSIFOV, 1963, 1976; GEORGIEV & HUBENOV, 2006; HUBENOV, 1992, 2008b). For Cerambycide this

fact is due to the deforestation of conifers in the first two vegetation belts. Probably because of this, many boreomontane and montane species that feed on conifers go down below 1000 m a.s.l. The Eurosiberian species comprised from 31.0% to 45.7% (from nine to 187 species) and from 30.5% to 43.0% (from 11 to 315 species) of the species composition of the separate vegetation belts of the Pirin and Rila Mts., respectively (Table 4). There were no significant differences in the vertical distribution of this group in the two mountains, except that in the subalpine and alpine zones some areographical categories were differently represented.

Mediterranean species (combined into 19 zoogeographical categories). These were 41 species (5.5%) from the Pirin Mts. and 45 species (4.5%) from the Rila Mts. They were represented mainly in the first three vegetation belts and their number rapidly decreased with altitude. Most of the Mediterranean species occur only in one or two vegetation belts (Table 2). A significant percentage of these species and their relatively scarce populations were due to the lower ecological flexibility of the Mediterranean forms in comparison with the Eurosiberian species. Because of the big variety of the areas, this group was divided into many subgroups with different origin, distribution and ecological peculiarities of the taxa. This complexity contributes to using various zoogeographical classifications for Bulgaria (JOSIFOV, 1981, 1986, 1988, 1999; GRUEV, 1988, 1995, 2000a, 2000b, 2000c, 2002; HEISS & JOSIFOV, 1990, GRUEV & KUSMANOV, 1994; HUBENOV, 1996, 2008a; GRUEV & BECHEV, 2000; POPOV, 2002). The Mediterranean species included from 2.0% to 10.3% (from one to 28 species) of Diptera of the separate vegetation belts of the two mountains (Table 4). The difference between the first vegetation belt of the Pirin (28 species – 10.3%) and Rila Mts. (19 species – 7.4%) was due to the fact that in the neighbouring region of the Pirin Mts., the Sandanski-Petrich Valley (the region with the strongest Mediterranean influence in Bulgaria), the Mediterranean forms in some Diptera families reached 17% (BESCHOVSKI & HUBENOV, 1986). The Holomediterranean (ten species – 1.3% from the Pirin Mts. and eight species – 0.8% from the Rila Mts.) and Mediterranean-Central Asian (six species each or 0.8-0.6% from the two mountains) species were the most numerous. The South European forms in the Rila Mts. were

more. In the subalpine belt four Mediterranean taxa were established: three from the Pirin and two from the Rila Mts. (*Prosimulium petrosorum* Rubtsov – South-east European species of the family Simuliidae, *Ogcodes lautereri* Chvala – Holomediterranean species of the family Acroceridae, *Lamproscatella unipunctata* Becker – Mediterranean-Central Asian species of the family Ephydriidae, also found in the alpine belt of the Pirin Mts., and *Sarcophaga porrecta* Böttcher – South European species of the family Sarcophagidae). These might be Montane Mediterranean forms or species with unclear distribution. When comparing with the Pirin Mts., there was a slightly higher percentage of the Mediterranean taxa which might be related to the specific natural conditions and geographical location of this mountain. There were no significant differences in the distribution of the well-represented areographical categories between the two mountains. Of the remaining categories, not all were presented in each of the mountains.

Endemics. This category included taxa, which were not distributed outside the Balkan Peninsula. The percentage of endemism was low in Diptera – 1.2-1.7% (13 species from the Pirin Mts. and 12 species from the Rila Mts.). The Bulgarian endemic forms prevailed. Endemic forms have not been established in the first two vegetation belts of the Rila Mts., unlike the Pirin Mts. The main part of the endemic species was related to the beech and coniferous belts (three – seven species or 0.8-2.3%). This suggests that these endemic species are post-glacial neoendemics which are to be connected with the Eurosiberian forms. Local endemics have not been established among Diptera of the two mountains. The dipterans included rare and mostly newly described taxa (from the Pirin Mts. – one in 1862, two in 1940 and 1942, and the others after 1970; from the Rila Mts. – one in 1930, one – in 1940 and all the others after 1970).

Conclusions

A total of 1351 dipteran species from 63 families have been established in the two mountains so far. The species known from the Pirin Mts. are 759 (18.5% of the Bulgarian species) and the species known from the Rila Mts. are 1003 (25.1% of the Bulgarian species). The de-

gree of similarity between the dipterans of the two mountains was low – 46.2%. The dipterous fauna could be divided into two main groups:

1) Species with Mediterranean type of distribution (49 species or 6.5% from the Pirin Mts. and 48 species or 4.8% from the Rila Mts.): more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic. Species of southern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group, as well;

2) Species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (710 species or 93.5% from the Pirin Mts. and 955 species or 95.2% from the Rila Mts.): more cold-resistant and more widely distributed in the Palaearctic. Species of northern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and outside of it, can be formally related to this group, as well.

The zoogeographical character of the dipteran fauna was determined by the second group. The percentage of the typical Mediterranean species of the two mountains were similar (4.5 and 5.5%). The ratio between the two main groups was different in the separate vegetation belts of the two mountains but without great percentage differences between the mountains themselves. The differences in the first vegetation belt of the two mountains were the biggest (10%).

Xerothermic oak forests (273 species or 36.8% from the Pirin Mts. and 256 species or 25.5% from the Rila Mts.). Of the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (32 species or 11.7% from the Pirin Mts. and 22 species or 8.6% from the Rila Mts.), the Holomediterranean, Mediterranean-Central Asian, North Mediterranean and South European species were the most numerous. Of the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (241 species or 88.3% from the Pirin Mts. and 234 species or 91.4% from the Rila Mts.) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species were best represented. Endemic forms have not been established yet in the Rila Mts.

Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic mixed forests (349 species or 47.0% from the Pirin Mts. and 351 species or 35.0% from the Rila Mts.). Of the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (23 species – 6.6% from the Pirin Mts. and 19 species – 5.4% from the Rila Mts.), the Mediterranean-Central Asian and

Holomediterranean prevail, and of the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (326 species or 93.4% from the Pirin Mts. and 332 species or 94.6% from the Rila Mts.) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian, and European species are best represented. The number of Holarctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, European-North African, Holoeurosiberian, West Eurosiberian, Disjunct Eurosiberian, and European species is increased. The percentage of the Mediterranean species decreases. Endemic forms have not been established yet in the Rila Mts.

Beech forests (409 species or 55.1% from the Pirin Mts. and 736 species or 73.4% from the Rila Mts.). Of the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (12 species or 2.9% from the Pirin Mts. and 23 species or 3.1% from the Rila Mts.), the Mediterranean-Central Asian and Holomediterranean were the most numerous, while of the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (397 species or 97.1% from the Pirin Mts. and 713 species or 96.9% from the Rila Mts.) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian, and European species were best represented. The species of southern type distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it were not presented in the Rila Mts. The number of Holarctic-Oriental, Palaearctic-Oriental, Holarctic, West Palaearctic, Holoeurosiberian, West and Central Eurosiberian, West Eurosiberian and European species has increased. Endemics have been established in the Rila Mts. Of the endemic taxa, the Bulgarian endemics prevailed. The percentage of the Mediterranean forms decreased.

Coniferous forests (265 species or 35.7% from the Pirin Mts. and 277 species or 27.6% from the Rila Mts.). Of the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (six species each – 2.3% from the Pirin Mts. and 2.2% from the Rila Mts.), the South European species were

the most numerous, while of the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (259 species or 97.7% from the Pirin Mts. and 271 species or 97.8% from the Rila Mts.), the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species prevailed. Of the areographical categories, 26 were not presented in the Pirin Mts. and 28 – in the Rila Mts. The Cosmopolitan, Holarctic-Oriental, Palaearctic-Oriental, West Palaearctic, European-North African and Disjunct Eurosiberian species were better represented. The percentage of the Mediterranean forms considerably decreased.

Subalpine vegetation (79 species or 10.6% from the Pirin Mts. and 99 species or 9.9% from the Rila Mts.). Of the species with Mediterranean type of distribution three species have been recorded from the Pirin Mts. and two – from the Rila Mts. Of the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (32 areographical categories of the Pirin Mts. and 31 – of the Rila Mts.), the Holarctic and European species were the most numerous. This part of the two mountains is poorly explored and excluding some families, the studies are fragmentary.

Alpine vegetation (29 species or 3.9% from the Pirin Mts. and 26 species or 2.6% from the Rila Mts.). One Mediterranean species (*Lamproscatella unipunctata* Becker of the family Ephyridae) were established from the Pirin Mts. and only species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution belonging to 16 areographical categories were established from the Rila Mts. The Holarctic and European taxa were the most numerous. The remaining categories were represented by one – two species each. One Bulgarian endemic (*Molophilus lautereri* Stary of the family Limoniidae) was recorded from the Rila Mts. With the exception of four families, studies on the two-winged insects in this vegetation belt of the Pirin and Rila Mountains are almost lacking.

References

- BESCHOVSKI V., HUBENOV Z. 1986. Die Insekten von der Familie Tachinidae (Diptera) in den Submediterraneanbiotopen Südwestbulgariens. I. Artenbestand und zoogeographische Charakteristik der Tachinidae im Tal zwischen Sandanski und Petrič. – In: BOTEV B., V. GOLEMANSKI, V. BESCHOVSKI and V. GEORGIEV (eds.): Fauna of Southwestern Bulgaria. 1. Sofia, Publishing house of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 118-129. (In Bulgarian with German summary).
- BONDEV I. 1991. The vegetation of Bulgaria. Kliment Ohridski University Press, Sofia. 184 p. (In Bulgarian with English summary).
- BONDEV I. 1997. Geobotanic regioning. – In: YORDANOVA M., D. DONCHEV (ed.): Geography of Bulgaria. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 269-305. (In Bulgarian with English summary).
- BONDEV I. 2002. Geobotanic regioning. – In: Geography of Bul-

- garia. ForCom, Sofia, 336-352. (In Bulgarian with English summary).
- DRENSKY P. 1929. Blutsaugende Fliegen aus der Familie der Tabanidae (Bremsen) in Bulgarien. – Mitteilungen königl naturwissenschaftlichen Instituten in Sofia (Bulgarien), **2**: 55-128. (In Bulgarian with German summary).
- GEORGIEV V. 1982. Zoogeographical regions on the basis of the land fauna. – In: Geography of Bulgaria. 1. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 472-477. (In Bulgarian with English summary).
- GEORGIEV V. 2002. Zoogeographic regioning. – In: Geography of Bulgaria. ForCom, Sofia, 373-375. (In Bulgarian with English summary).
- GEORGIEV G., HUBENOV Z. 2006. Vertical distribution and zoogeographical characteristics of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) family in Bulgaria. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **58** (3): 315-343.
- GORODKOV K. B. 1984. Ranges types of insects of tundra and forests zones of European Part of USSR. – In: Provisional Atlas of the insects of the European Part of USSR. Leningrad, Nauka, 3-20. (In Russian)
- GRUEV B. 1988. General biogeography. Nauka i iskustvo, Sofia. 396 p. (In Bulgarian)
- GRUEV B. 1995. About the mediterranean faunistic complex in Bulgaria. – *Annuaire de l'Université de Sofia "Kliment Ohridski", Faculté de Biologie*, **86/87** (1 – Zoology): 75-82.
- GRUEV B. 2000a. Souteuropean peninsular endemism of Alticinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae). – *Travaux Scientifiques Université de Plovdiv, Animalia*, **36** (6): 35-50.
- GRUEV B. 2000b. About the Atlantic faunistic element in Bulgaria. – *Travaux Scientifiques Université de Plovdiv, Animalia*, **36** (6): 67-72. (in Bulgarian, English summary)
- GRUEV B. 2000c. About the submediterranean zone of the Palearctic realm and the submediterranean faunistic element in Bulgaria. – *Travaux Scientifiques Université de Plovdiv, Animalia*, **36** (6): 73-94. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- GRUEV B. 2002. A comparative study on Alticinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) in the Balkan Peninsula and Asiatic Turkey. Causes of the similarities and the differences of the fauna. – *Travaux Scientifiques Université de Plovdiv, Animalia*, **38**(6): 49-79.
- GRUEV B., BECHEV D. 2000. Zoogeographical belonging of the leaf beetle species of Lamprosomatinae, Eumolpinae, Chrysomelinae, Alticinae, Hispinae и Cassidinae (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) and their distribution in the biogeographical regions of Bulgaria. – *Travaux Scientifiques Université de Plovdiv, Animalia*, **36** (6): 5-34. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- GRUEV B., KUSMANOV B. 1994. General biogeography. University K. Ohridski, Sofia. 498 p. (In Bulgarian).
- GRUEV B., KUSMANOV B. 1999. General biogeography. Plovdiv University, Plovdiv. 344 p. (In Bulgarian).
- HEISS E., JOSIFOV M. 1990. Vergleichende Untersuchung über Artenspektrum, Zoogeographie und Ökologie der Heteropteren-Fauna in Hochgebirgen Österreichs und Bulgariens. – *Bericht des Naturwissenschaftlich-Medizinischen Vereins Innsbruck*, **77**: 123-161.
- HUBENOV Z. 1992. Artenbestand, Höhenferbreitung und zoogeographische Charakteristik der Familie Tachinidae (Diptera) aus dem Pirin-gebirge. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **44**: 3-18.
- HUBENOV Z. 1993. Höhenverbreitung der Familie Tachinidae (Diptera) in Bulgarien. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **46**: 24-38.
- HUBENOV Z. 1995. Artenbestand, Vertikalverbreitung und zoogeographische Charakteristik der Familie Tachinidae (Diptera) aus dem Belasiza-Gebirge. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **48**: 48-61.
- HUBENOV Z. 1996. Zoogeographische Charakteristik der bulgarischen Raupenfliegen (Diptera, Tachinidae). – *Historia Naturalis bulgarica*, **6**: 49-58.
- HUBENOV Z. 2004. Estimation of the faunistic diversity of the Eastern Rhodopes. – In: BERON, P., POPOV A. (eds.). Biodiversity of Bulgaria. 2. Biodiversity of Eastern Rhodopes (Bulgarian and Greece). Pensoft & National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, 941-951.
- HUBENOV Z. 2008a. Recent fauna of Bulgaria – Animalia: Invertebrata. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **60** (1): 3-21.
- HUBENOV Z. 2008b. Composition and zoogeographical characteristics of the family Tachinidae (Insecta: Diptera) in the Balkan Countries. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **60** (3): 243-265.
- HUBENOV Z. 2014. Faunistic diversity. – In: POPOV A. (ed.). The natural bounthy of Vitosha Nature Park. Vitosha Nature Park Directorate, Sofia, 93-95. (In Bulgarian).
- HUBENOV Z. 2015a. Areographical structure of the Bulgarian non-marine invertebrate fauna (Metazoa: Invertebrata). – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **67** (2): 203-213.
- HUBENOV Z. 2015b. Two-winged insects (Insecta: Diptera) of Pirin. – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, **21**: 215-256.
- HUBENOV Z. 2015c. Comparative zoogeographical review of the tachinid fauna (Diptera: Tachinidae) of the Belasitsa and Slavyanka mountains. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **67** (3): 351-364.
- HUBENOV Z. 2016. Two-winged insects (Insecta: Diptera) of Rila. – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, **23**:
- HUBENOV Z., BESHOVSKI V., JOSIFOV M., POPOV A., KUMANSKI K., SAKALIAN V., ABADJIEV S., VIDINOVA Y., LYUBOMIROV T. 2000. Entomofaunistic diversity of the Central Balkan National Park. – In: Biological diversity of the Central Balkan National Park, Sofia Pensoft, 319-362, 491-512, 538-586.
- JOAKIMOFF D. 1899. Prinos kam faunata ot nasekomi na Rila planina (Contribution to the insect fauna of Rila Mountain). – *Periodichesko spisanie na Balgarskoto knizhovno druzhestvo* (Periodical Journal of the Bulgarian Literary Society), **60**: 858-884. (in Bulgarian).
- JOSIFOV M. 1963. Heteropteren aus der Umgebung von Petrič (SW Bulgarien). – *Bulletin de l'Institut de zoologique et Musee (Academie Bulgare des sciences)*, **13**: 93-132. (In Bulgarian with German summary).
- JOSIFOV M. 1976. Artbildung bei den Heteropteren im Mittelmeerraum als Folge der postglazialen Disjunktion ihrer Areale. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **4**: 11-19. (In Bulgarian with German summary).
- JOSIFOV M. 1981. Nasekomite ot razred Heteroptera na Balkanskiya poluostrov. Dr. Sci. Thesis, Sofia, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Instute of Zoology), 31-288. (In Bulgarian).
- JOSIFOV M. 1986. Verzeichnis der von der Balkanhalbinsel bekannten Heteropterenarten (Insecta, Heteroptera). – *Faunistische Abhandlungen Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde Dresden*, **14** (6): 61-93.
- JOSIFOV M. 1988. Über den zoogeographischen Charakter der Südeuropäischen Insektenfauna unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Heteropteren. – *Berichte des Naturwissenschaftlich-Medizinischen Vereins in Innsbruck*, **75**: 177-184.
- JOSIFOV M. 1999. Heteropterous insects in the Sandanski-Petrič

- Kettle, Southwestern Bulgaria. – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, **10**: 35-66.
- KOVACHEV S. 2000. Qualitative structure and distribution of Blackflies (Diptera: Simuliidae) from high mountain streams of glacial origin in the Rila Mountains. – In: GOLEMSNSKI V, NAIDENOV W (eds.). Biodiversity and evolution of glacial water ecosystems in the Rila Mountains. Institute of Zoology, BAS, Sofia, 67-74.
- KRYZHANOVSKY O. 1965. Composition and origin of the terrestrial fauna of Central Asia (based chiefly on the beetles material). Nauka, Moscow-Leningrad. 430 p. (In Russian).
- LATTIN DE G. 1967. Grundriss der Zoogeographie. Hochschul-lehrbücher für Biologie. 12. VEB Gustav Fischer Verlag, Jena. 602 p.
- LOPATIN I. K. 1989. Zoogeography. Vysheyschaya shkola, Minsk. 392 p. (in Russian).
- MALICKY H., ANT H., ASPÖCK H., DE JONG R., THALER K., VARGA Z. 1983. Argumente zur Existenz und Chorologie mittel-europäischer (extramediterran-europäischer) Faunen-Elemente. – *Entomologia Generalis*, **9**: 101-119.
- NEDELKOV N. 1909. Nashata entomologichna fauna. – *Arhiv na Ministerstvoto na narodnoto prosveshtenie*, **1** (3): 83-135. (In Bulgarian).
- NEDELKOV N. 1910. Beitrag zu Diptera Bulgariens. – *Internationale entomologische Zeitschrift*, **4** (7): 36-37.
- NEDELKOV N. 1912. Sixth contribution to the entomological fauna of Bulgaria. – *Revue Academy Sciences de Bulgarie*, **2**: 177-218. (In Bulgarian).
- POPOV A. 2002. Zoogeographical analysis of Neuroptera in Bulgaria. – *Acta zoologica hungarica*, **48** (Suppl. 2): 271-180.
- STANEV. 1991. Climatic regions of Bulgaria. – In: *The climate of Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 53-89. (In Bulgarian).
- STOICHEV S. 2000a. The zoobenthos from several glacial lakes in the Rila Mountains, Bulgaria. – In: GOLEMSNSKI V, NAIDENOV W (eds.). Biodiversity and evolution of glacial water ecosystems in the Rila Mountains. Institute of Zoology, BAS, Sofia, 155-162.
- STOICHEV S. 2000b. Zoobenthos in outflows of some glacial lakes in the Rila Mountains. – In: GOLEMSNSKI V, NAIDENOV W (eds.). Biodiversity and evolution of glacial water ecosystems in the Rila Mountains. Institute of Zoology, BAS, Sofia, 163-168.
- STOICHEV S. 2002. Hydrofaunistic investigation of the Urdini Ezera Glacial Lakes, Northwestern Rila Mountains, West Bulgaria. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **54** (1): 63-68.
- STOICHEV S. 2004. The benthic Invertebrates in the Marichini Ezera Glacial Lakes, Eastern Rila Mountains, South-Wewst Bulgaria. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **56** (1): 277-282.
- STOICHEV S., CHERNEV N. 2001. On the Chironomid fauna from Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River (Rila Mountain, Southwest Bulgaria). – *Lauterbornia*, **40**: 119-121.
- STOICHEV S., DANOVA E. 2003. Hydrofaunistic investigation of the Mussalenski Ezera Glacial Lakes, Eastern Rila Mountains, South-Wewst Bulgaria. – *Acta zoologica bulgarica*, **55** (2): 75-80.
- STOJANOV N. 1966. Rastitelna pokrivka. – In: BESHKOV, A. (ed.): *Geography of Bulgaria*. 1. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 447-482. (In Bulgarian).
- VELCHEV V. 1997. Features and regularities of distribution of contemporary vegetation. – In: YORDANOVA M., D. DONCHEV (ed.): *Geography of Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 265-269. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- VELCHEV V. 2002. Characteristic features and regularities in the distribution of the present-day vegetation. – In: COPRALEV I. et al. (ed.): *Geography of Bulgaria*. ForKom, Sofia, 321-324. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- VELCHEV V., GANCHEV S., BONDEV I. 1982. Rastitelni poyasi. – In: GALABOV, Zh. (ed.): *Geography of Bulgaria*. 1. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 439-443. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- VELCHEV V. BONDEV I., KOCHEV H., RUSSAKOVA V., VASSILEV P., MESHINEV T., NIKOLOV V., GEORGIEV N., VALCHEV V. 1989. Vegetation. – In: MISHEV K. (ed.): *Natural and economic potential of the mountains in Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 273-337. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- VELCHEV V., S. TONKOV. 1986. Vegetation and flora of Southwest Bulgaria. – In: BOTEV, B. (ed.): *Fauna of Southwestern Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 20-43. (In Bulgarian with English summary)
- VIGNA TAGLIANTI A., AUDISIO P., BIONDI M., BOLOGNA M., CARPANETO G., BIASE A., FATTORINI S., PIATTELLA E., SINDACO R. 1999. A proposal for a chorotype classification of the Near East fauna, in the framework of the Western Palaearctic Region. – *Biogeographia*, **20**: 31-59.

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Вертикално разпространение и сравнителна зоогеографска характеристика на диптерната фауна (Insecta: Diptera) в растителните пояси на планините Пирин и Рила

Здравко ХУБЕНОВ

(Резюме)

В двете планини са установени общо 1351 вида от 63 семейства (759 вида на Пирин и 1003 вида на Рила). Ниското сходство на фауната между тези планини (46.2%) е свързано с техните специфични природни особености и недостатъчно проучване. Най-много видове са намерени в пояса на буковите гори (409 – 55.1% на Пирин и 736 – 73.4% на Рила). Сходството на диптерната фауна между растителните пояси на двете планини се колебае от 0% до 46.6%. Диптерите са разпределени в 92 ареалографски категории, обособени в 2 надгрупи 1) видове с медитерански тип на разпространение (49 вида – 6.5% на Пирин и 48 вида – 4.8% на Рила) – по-топлолюбиви и разпространени предимно в южните части на Палеарктика, към които са прибавени и видовете от южен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика; 2) видове с палеарктичен и евросибирски тип на разпространение (710 вида – 93.5% на Пирин и 955 вида – 95.2% на Рила) – по-еврибионтни и по-широко разпространени в Палеарктика, към които формално са отнесени и видовете от северен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика. От първата група най-много са холомедитеранските и медитераноцентралноазиатските форми (0.6% до 1.3%). От втората група преобладават европейски, холарктични, холоевросибирски и транспалеарктични таксони (7.8% до 19.0%). Ендемични са 12-13 вида (1.2% до 1.7%). Разгледано е разпределението на зоогеографските категории в отделните растителни пояси на планините.